

ABSTRACTS

BOOK

**INTERNATIONAL
CONFERENCE
BIOMED2024
12-14 MAY, 2024
SHEKVETILI, GEORGIA**

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Search for new methods for cancer diagnosis

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Abstract

Numerous cellular components are being studied to identify new possibilities for effective cancer diagnosis. Researchers have proposed proteins, miRNA, micronuclei, DNA, and other biochemical or cytological objects as potential markers and targets for disease detection and management. Often quantitative changes of these objects, increase or decrease, are observed in the blood serum of patients, which correlates with the severity of the disease or the effectiveness of treatment. In this regard, today, as never before, the issue of cancer management is acute and the study of cellular proteins is highly appropriate and effective. Management of cellular processes is associated with the activation and inhibition of various metabolic pathways. Typically, manipulating a single protein causes a chain initiation of multiple reactions. It is therefore difficult to say unequivocally that quantitative modification, activation or inhibition of this or that protein may be an unconditional marker or target to solve the above-mentioned problem. It is common for proteins already recognized as markers to manifest themselves differently in individuals. We therefore believe that the study of diagnostic agents should be conducted in a complex manner parallel to the metabolic pathways associated with corresponding proteins. We investigated changes of ubiquitin levels in blood serum of cancer patients and healthy volunteers. Elisa test and subsequent statistical analysis were used for assessment. The results indicate the necessity of further investigation of ubiquitin and other proteins that may react or indirectly affect ubiquitin level variability.

Keywords: cancer; ubiquitin; diagnostics

1. Introduction

The expediency of quantitative changes in the regulatory protein ubiquitin has been suggested by a number of scientists to explore new ways of cancer diagnosis. Ubiquitin is involved in the management of virtually every cellular process, both directly and indirectly, due to its diverse functions. The structural conservatism of ubiquitin warrants it to participate in

protein trafficking, degradation, and synthesis, as well as in stimulating and inhibiting protein functions. These functions are performed with or without the involvement of the ubiquitin-26 proteasome multicomponent systems [1]. Ubiquitin is covalently conjugated to cellular proteins in the cytoplasm and nucleus of eukaryotic cells by the conjugating enzymes. In this process, several ubiquitin monomers are usually sequentially linked to each other. The multi-ubiquitin chain acts as a signal for degradation of target proteins in the 26S proteasome. Proteolysis by ubiquitin regulates various processes in the cell, including stress response, cell cycle, gene expression, and apoptosis [2]. Ubiquitin is involved in the pathogenesis of various diseases. Increase in extracellular ubiquitin levels have been reported in patients with neurodegenerative, muscular, cerebral and cardiac ischemic, cancerous, rheumatoid, and other diseases. Cell ubiquitin has been suggested to be involved in the production of amyloid inclusions and the regulation of hematopoiesis [3]. In recent decades, numerous studies have been devoted to elucidation of the molecular mechanisms involved in metabolism in the cancer reprogramming process [4]. Ubiquitination and deubiquitination are actively considered as modulators of cancer metabolism [5]. Unregulated ubiquitination and deubiquitination play an important role in reprogramming signaling pathways of tumor cell by modulating transcription factors and enzymes, like ligases and DUBs (deubiquitinating enzymes), involved in metabolism [Fig. 1]. Therefore, ubiquitin balance in cancer metabolism requires more research [6-8].

Fig.1. Schematic representation of the roles of E3 ligases and DUBs in regulating stem cell differentiation and stem cell maintenance.

Researchers have proposed proteins, miRNA, micronuclei, DNA, and other biochemical or cytological objects as potential markers and targets for disease detection and management [Tab. 1]. Often quantitative changes of these

objects, increase or decrease, are observed in the blood serum of patients, which correlates with the severity of the disease or the effectiveness of treatment. Vast amount of proteins and peptides is considered as potential prognostic biomarkers to identify new possibilities for effective diagnosis [9].

Main goals of cancer research are:

- To elucidate the biochemical and genetic mechanisms that underlie the uncontrolled growth of cancer cells
- To elucidate the biochemical and genetic mechanisms that underlie ability of cancer cells to invade and metastasize
- To develop successful treatments that destroy cancer cells, while causing minimal damage to normal cells
- To identify protein markers for diagnostics and assessment of effectiveness of treatment.

In the search for effective diagnosis, the study of biologically active proteins is intensive. An innovative approach in this process is to explore proteins for which ubiquitin is a very favorable object because of its key characteristics. Ubiquitin is a natural serum protein with a conservative structure in the mammalian class and possesses high thermal, structural, and proteolytic stability. We suggest determining the importance of calculating cellular ubiquitin levels for the diagnosis of cancer and the ability to predict fluctuations in cell ubiquitin levels detected in the plasma of cancer patients [10].

Table 1
 Front. Mol. Biosci., 27 August 2018 |
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmolb.2018.00076>

MOLECULAR DIAGNOSTICS IN ONCOLOGY			
HEREDITARY CANCER SYNDROMES	PREDICTIVE MARKERS	CIRCULATING TUMOR FRAGMENTS	CARCINOMAS OF UNKNOWN PRIMARY
ASSAYS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ RECURRENT MUTATIONS (PCR) ▪ SINGLE-GENE ANALYSIS (SANGER SEQUENCING, MLPA) ▪ MULTIGENE PANELS (NGS) ▪ WHOLE EXOME SEQUENCING 	ASSAYS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ DNA ▪ RNA ▪ PROTEINS ▪ CELLS ▪ TISSUE SLICES ▪ PDXs 	ASSAYS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ CTCs ▪ ctDNA ▪ RNA ▪ PROTEINS 	ASSAYS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ SINGLE MARKERS ▪ INTEGRATIVE ASSAYS
CANCER PATIENTS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ RISK OF 2ND MALIGNANCY ▪ CHOICE OF TREATMENT 	MOLECULAR TARGETS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ HER2 ▪ EGFR-MUT ▪ BRAF-MUT ▪ ALK ▪ ROS 	CANCER PATIENTS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ CONTROL OF TUMOR ERADICATION ▪ MONITORING OF TUMOR BURDEN ▪ CHOICE OF THERAPY 	TISSUE-SPECIFIC MARKERS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ RNA ▪ PROTEINS
HEALTHY PEOPLE <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ IDENTIFICATION OF SUBJECTS AT-RISK 	TUMOR PHENOTYPES <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MSI-H ▪ BRCAness ▪ MUTATION BURDEN 	HEALTHY PEOPLE <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ EARLY DIAGNOSIS 	TUMOR-SPECIFIC MARKERS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ POINT MUTATIONS ▪ GENE REARRANGEMENTS ▪ COPY NUMBER VARIATIONS

2. Materials and Methods

Blood collection and serum preparation Blood was collected for conducting regular blood tests. The serum was prepared 10 minutes after taking the blood in gel-clot test tubes at room temperature. Then the serum was transferred to the Ependorf test tubes and stored at -8 degrees.

Elisa test Serum ubiquitin levels have been measured by Elisa test. Human Ubiquitin Elisa kit provided from LifeSpan Bioscience Inc. is a 96-well enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay for the quantitative detection of Human Ubiquitin in samples of Serum. Procedures were conducted according to the protocol proposed by the corporation. Absorbance on a plate was read at 450 nm wavelength, dilution 1: 100.

Statistical analysis Statistical methods OriginPro, ImageJ and ANOVA were used for quantitative analysis. Grouping of patients was made according diagnosis and control healthy group of volunteers. Research involving human participants performed in accordance with the requirements of the Council of Europe Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine, Biomedical Research, as well as the UNESCO Declaration of Bioethics and Human Rights and regulations established by the New Vision University Hospital ethic committee (Protocol N07/05.06.2017). We have obtained consent letters from volunteers to use their biological material for research.

3. Results

We aimed to study the quantitative changes of ubiquitin in the blood serum of patients with various diagnoses in order to show its diagnostic potential. In collaboration with several clinics, patients' blood serum was collected in the first phase of the study. The study was conducted using immunological methods. 70 patients and healthy volunteers were examined. Elisa quantitative test results and subsequent statistical analysis of the results of the immunological study showed quantitative differences in ubiquitin levels for divergent tumor diagnoses. The amount of extracellular ubiquitin varies widely according to the diagnosis. The results are as follows: Ovarian adenocarcinoma $13,6 \pm 6,2$ ng/ml, Breast invasive carcinoma $33,6 \pm 8,9$ ng/ml, Gastric adenocarcinoma $13,4 \pm 4,6$ ng/ml, Intestinal gastric, rectal adenocarcinomas $25,8 \pm 4$ ng/ml, Lung carcinoma $54 \pm 13,2$ ng/ml, Cervical squamous cell carcinoma $37,9 \pm 8,6$ ng/ml, Cervical adenocarcinoma 94 ± 4.0 ng/ml. Significant differences in the serum ubiquitin levels of patients with different diagnoses compared with data from a control group of healthy volunteers - 31.7 ± 3.9 ng/ml, indicate that it is not yet possible to discuss quantitative changes in ubiquitin for

diagnosis [Tab. 2].

70 patients and healthy volunteers were examined. Elisa quantitative test results and subsequent statistical analysis of the results of the immunological study showed quantitative differences in ubiquitin levels for divergent tumor diagnoses. The amount of extracellular ubiquitin varies widely according to the diagnosis. The results are as follows: Ovarian adenocarcinoma $13,6\pm 6,2$ ng/ml, Breast invasive carcinoma $33,6\pm 8,9$ ng/ml, Gastric adenocarcinoma $13,4\pm 4,6$ ng/ml, Intestinal gastric, rectal adenocarcinomas $25,8\pm 4$ ng/ml, Lung carcinoma $54\pm 13,2$ ng/ml, Cervical squamous cell carcinoma $37,9\pm 8,6$ ng/ml, Cervical adenocarcinoma 94 ± 4.0 ng/ml (Fig. 2).

Table 2
Comparison of ubiquitin concentration in blood serum of patients with various diagnosis.

N	Cancer Type	Ub ng/ml
1	Ovarian adenocarcinoma 4 stage	13.6 ± 6.2
2	Breast invasive carcinoma 4 stage	33.6 ± 8.9
3	Gastric adenocarcinoma 3 stage	13.4 ± 4.6
4	Intestinal gastric and rectal adenocarcinoma	25.8 ± 4.5
5	Lung Carcinoma	54 ± 13.2
6	Cervical squamous cell carcinoma	37.9 ± 8.6
7	Cervical adenocarcinoma	94 ± 4
8	Other	41.4 ± 8.5
9	Healthy	31.73 ± 3.9

4. Discussion

The source of extracellular ubiquitin may be the passive release from cells during physiological processes such as apoptosis and necrosis, but some authors note the ubiquitin extraction from normal cells. To date, many aspects of extracellular ubiquitin activity remain unclear, spatially as to its possible pathways and role in the various cellular processes associated with malignant tumors. Cellular ubiquitin is considered a biomarker of the disease because many diseases are associated with increased ubiquitin concentrations in body fluids [11]. Ubiquitin activity is observed to be dysregulated in various kinds of cancers.

Ubiquitination and deubiquitination can be abnormally regulated by transcriptional, translational, posttranslational or epigenetic mechanisms in cancer cells, exerting oncogenic or anticancer roles in carcinogenesis. The process of ubiquitin system participation in cancer progression, metastasis

and probability of ubiquitin use for diagnostics requires thorough research [4,12]. Management of cellular processes is carried out through the activation and inhibition of various metabolic pathways. Typically, manipulating a single protein causes a chain initiation of multiple reactions. It is therefore difficult to say unequivocally that quantitative modification, activation or inhibition of this or that protein may be an unconditional marker or target to solve the above-mentioned problem. It is common for proteins already recognized as markers to manifest themselves differently in individuals. We therefore believe that the study of proteins should be conducted in a complex manner parallel to the metabolic pathways associated with these proteins.

Fig.2. Study the quantitative changes of ubiquitin in the blood serum of patients with various diagnoses in order to show its diagnostic potential.

5. Conclusions

In recent years, the involvement of ubiquitination and deubiquitination within the regulation of metabolic reprogramming in cancer cells has received a growing attention. Given the complexity and importance of both cancer metabolism and protein ubiquitination, the precise roles of protein ubiquitin in metabolic reprogramming are worth further studies and analyses. The issue requires further investigation to determine the reasons for the sharp increase or decrease in protein relative to the norm and what accompanying metabolic processes should be considered for the effectiveness of the diagnosis. Today, as never before, the issue of cancer management is acute. In this regard, the study of cellular proteins is highly appropriate and effective. More than one protein for identification of some types of tumors are necessary, otherwise diagnostics can be complicated and misinterpreted.

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Sex related differences in rat's behavior and brain morphology after the toxic effect of manganese

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Abstract

Exposure to heavy metals is a common phenomenon, which is due to contaminated drinking water and industrial activities. The toxic effect of different forms of metals is not only related to the environment, but also related to the metabolism and detoxification mechanism of the organism. In order to explore the difference of manganese toxicity on male and female rats, we studied the impact of manganese compounds on rat behavior and brain morphology. Four-week-old Wistar rats with body weight between 80-120g (n=42, including 21 males and 21 females) were studied. Wistar rats were assigned to four groups: rats in control groups (male, female) were given regular water, while rats in other groups drank water with final manganese concentration of 15 mg/ml (male, female) for three months. To study exploratory and anxiety behavior rats were tested in open field, home cage and elevated plus maze. To estimate learning and memory status multi-branched maze was used. The behavioral disturbance of male rats was more noticeable than that of female rats in the same group. It is found that excessive manganese ions also had more toxic effects on male animals than females. It was revealed that manganese poisoning increased Mn contents in the brains of both genders, caused slight damage of neurons, and produced notable gliosis. However, in hippocampus there were bioaccumulation differences between gender. Excess amount of manganese in the brain had a strong impact on learning processes. It was concluded that, under this experimental design, Mn exposure causes metal deposition in CNS. The effect of this

dose of manganese was gender-dependent and males had more pronounced behavioral damage compared to females, but females had an indication of motor damage. Gender differences in neuron morphology were not due to differential accumulation of Mn in brain regions. But the effect of manganese exposure was not similar in all observed brain regions (Motor Cortex, Prefrontal Cortex, Hippocampus-CA1, CA3 area and Dentate Gyrus).

Keywords: manganese; rat; behavior; neurotoxicity; gender

1. Introduction

Manganese (Mn) is an essential metal found in abundance in the environment and is necessary for numerous biochemical processes in the human body. Its function arises secondary to its inclusion in protein structures as a cofactor. Without its presence, the immune function of the human body, biochemical regulation of energy consumption, growth potential, coagulation and hemostatic function, as well as the mechanisms for removing the by-products of aberrant oxidative stress would be significantly weakened [1]. Optimal nutritional sources of Mn come primarily from plants, but supplementation with vitamins or healthy food is another important contribution. Drinking water often contains trace amounts of Mn with defined thresholds measured to prevent toxic effects. Another beneficial source of manganese for newborns is breast milk and formula, which prevents manganese deficiency during the critical period of infant development [2,3]. Manganese is an essential element, but excessive exposure to manganese is toxic. The main toxic effects associated with this metal are extrapyramidal side effects. Those disturbances closely resemble the symptoms of Parkinson's syndrome. These side effects are due to the changes in its deposition in certain components of the basal ganglia and changes in the activity of dopaminergic neuronal enzymes. Other notable effects include cardiotoxicity, hepatotoxicity, and increased infant mortality [4,5]. Sex differences in the prevalence, severity and progression of diseases of the nervous system are becoming increasingly important in biomedical research, motivated by gender-dependent behavior and physiology. Substantial evidence from recent neuroimaging studies supports gender differences in the structure and function of the human brain, starting in utero and continuing throughout the life. Long-term studies demonstrate persistent sexual dimorphism in brain trajectories, especially in the early adolescence. Endogenous developmental programming, developmental experience and/or environmental influence may become one of the reasons of arising sex differences in brain development. Sex and gender-related behavioral differences in infancy and childhood have been reported, which

are associated with differences in early exposure to chemicals. A better understanding of gender-specific differential vulnerability to neurotoxicants may provide insight into sexual brain dimorphism, behavior, mental health, and mental disorders [6]. Studies of the population not exposed to high Mn levels have shown conflicting results. According to some studies men have decreased absorption of Mn from the gastrointestinal tract, lower ferritin levels, and slower Mn clearance than women. Several studies show that, in a healthy, unaffected population, serum manganese levels are higher in males than in females [7]. However, there are some more recent reports showing no gender difference in baseline serum manganese levels. One recent study examined the intellectual function of children living in the Mexican mining region of Mn. Children exposed to Mn had higher levels of Mn in their hair and blood ($20\times$) than children not exposed to high levels of Mn. Girls exposed to manganese performed worse on the revised Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children than boys exposed to manganese. Although there were no gender differences in Mn levels in exposed children, this suggests that cognitive ability may be affected differently in boys and girls. Gender differences are not identified and unique to Mn. Human studies have also found gender differences in the storage and sensitivity of other metals. Similar features are indicated for cadmium (Cd), lead (Pb), Mn, mercury (Hg), and nickel (Ni) [8]. Animal studies also show gender differences in toxicokinetic and metal sensitivity. For example, male and female rats accumulate Mn differently in body tissues after exposure to Mn by inhalation; however, there were no differences in Mn accumulation in the striatum or other regions of the basal ganglia. Gender differences in toxicokinetic after a single oral dose of methylcyclopentadienyl manganese tricarbonyl (MMT) gasoline supplement showed that female rats accumulate higher MMT levels than male rats, due to slower MMT clearance. Erickson and his colleagues (2004a) exposed young rats to manganese by air for 13 weeks and found gender-specific changes in glutamine synthetase protein and mRNA expression, metallothionein mRNA, and glutathione levels in many areas of the brain. Gender differences in the toxicokinetic of Mn are present regardless of the route of administration and the type of Mn. Like humans, rodents show gender differences when exposed to other metals such as Pb and Hg [7]. We decided to evaluate potential gender-related differences in response to Manganese exposure.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Animals and experimental design

42 Wistar rats - 21 females and 21 males (P-28-30 at the initial day of

experiments) were used in our experiment. Rats in control groups drank regular water, and rats in experimental groups got water containing Mn in dose 15 mg/ml (Sodium arsenite (NaAsO₂) purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Cat. N S7400) for 3 months. Rats were kept on regular light/dark cycles throughout the procedures with ad libitum access to food. Care of animals during/after procedure(s) animals were transferred to the testing room and allowed to adapt to this room prior to testing. Animals were monitored while in the arena and returned to the home cage immediately after testing. All experimental procedures were approved by Animal Studies Committee of Georgian Ivane Beritashvili Center of Experimental Biomedicine and are in accordance with guidelines of the EC Ethical Directives.

2.2. Behavioral tests

Animals were subjected to following behavioral tests:

2.3. Open field test

This test is used to evaluate the exploratory and anxiety behavior of rat. Equipment: The Open Field is a circular arena with a diameter of 100 cm with walls 30 cm high. The floor is divided up into quarters with a central circle of 33cm diameter in the middle of the arena. Normal laboratory up lighting is required. Each animal is placed in the central circle and is observed for 5 min. The following events are recorded: ambulation - the number of grid lines crossed with all four paws; number of entries into the center of the open field; rearing - the number of times the animal stood on its hind limbs; hole reflex - looking into holes; grooming and defecation.

2.4. Elevated Plus Maze (EPM)

The EPM is a widely used rodent behavioral test that is utilized to assess anxiety-related behavior. The EPM apparatus consists of four arms: two open, and two closed arms, the apparatus is elevated 50-70 cm from the floor. Each arm is 50 cm long and 5 cm wide, and the closed arms were shielded by 25 cm high side end walls. The four arms were linked at a central square (the junction). Briefly, rats are placed at the junction of the four arms of the maze, facing an open arm, and entries/duration in each arm are recorded by a video-tracking system and observer simultaneously for 5 min. Other ethological parameters (i.e., rears, head dips and stretched-attend postures) can also be observed. An increase in open arm activity (duration and/or entries) reflects anti-anxiety behavior. In our laboratory, rats are exposed to the plus maze on one occasion; thus, results can be obtained in 5 min per rodent.

The Resident-Intruder - RI test (20) was used to determine the level of animal intraspecific territorial aggression. The test consists of the following: 1 weeks before testing the rat (so called “resident”) is placed in the experimental chamber (40x24x35 cm) and after 30 min the other rat (so called “intruder”),

weighing 20-30 grams less than the “resident” is placed into the chamber. Duration of the test is 10 minutes. The aim of the test is to record the following indices: First attack latency time, Number of attacks, Duration of attacks, Lateral threat, Offensive upright and keep down, Clinch, Chase/flight, Investigating opponent, Ano-genital sniffing, Grooming, Exploration.

2.5. Learning processing multi-branched maze

The process of learning is studied by means of multi-branched maze consisting from footbridges, mounted on props of 30 cm height. To move on an optimum trajectory animal is learning by a trial-and-error method. With the purpose of adaptation, all groups of animals for a few days are placed in a nest-box prior to the beginning of experiments. This nest-box is located at the exit platform of maze. At the beginning of the experiment an animal is placed on the start-platform and it has to find out the correct way to the nest-box. Process of learning proceeds without any food reinforcement and it can be described as follow: each passage of the crotch (when the animal has an opportunity of a choice of a direction) serves as a stimulus for further movement. Getting in a deadlock branch of the maze (error) and necessity of returning should be considered as a punishment for error and, probably, forces rat to avoid errors and to continue search for a right direction. It is possible to consider deliverance from nonethologic conditions (being on a maze platform) at the moment of hit in a nest-box as a reward and it serves as a motivation for maze learning. Each group of animals during 10 days was trained to pass a maze. The maze task was presented to each animal 5 times a day with at least 30 min intervals. The learning process is estimated by maze test performance (to reach the nest-box) within 5 min - by number of errors made during ambulation through the maze (enter into the blind-alley section) and by the time of maze passage. For estimation of learning process, Mn was given to experimental animals for 3 months before the maze test. For evaluation of memory tests, animals were subjected to maze session 2 months later after the termination of the learning test.

2.6. Nissl staining

Animals were deeply anesthetized with ketamine (100mg/kg) and then perfused transcardially with 4% paraformaldehyde in 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 7.4). Excised brains were post-fixed at 4°C in the same fixative for another 24 h and then cryoprotected in a 30% sucrose-solution. For Nissl staining 15- μ m coronal sections were cut on a cryostat (Microm HM 500 M). Every 6th section was collected and mounted on a poly-L-lysine coated glass slides. The slides were remained to dry, rehydrated with 100% alcohol, 95% alcohol, and distilled water. Subsequently, the sections were stained in 0.1% Cresyl violet (Sigma-Aldrich, Cat. N C504 solution). The sections were then

differentiated in 95% ethyl alcohol, dehydrated in 100% alcohol, and rinsed in xylene. Finally, the sections were mounted and observed under a light microscope (Leica DM LB). Cell counting in hippocampal CA1, CA3 areas, Dentate Gyrus, prefrontal and motor cortex was conducted blindly. For this purpose, the systematic random sampling was employed. The 2-dimensional counting grid (250 μm x 250 μm) at the magnification 400x was used. Totally 10-12 sections from each level within experimental and control animals were selected (35 randomly chosen range of visions at the same site of all sections from each animal).

2.7. Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using GraphPad Prism version 7.00 La Jolla California USA. Behavioral data from the different trial days were analyzed using repeated measures one-way ANOVA followed by post hoc Tukey's multiple comparison tests. Unpaired t-test with Welch's correction was used to determine a statistically significant difference between the two groups. $P < 0.05$ were considered statistically significant. All data are presented as Mean \pm SEM.

3. Results

Obtained data support the hypothesis that excess manganese in the body is one of the immediate causes of enhancement of interspecific predatory aggressive and violent behavior in rats. Aggression increased in 37.5 percent of female animals and 42 percent of male animals (Fig.1). It should also be noted that, aggressive attacks in male rats were more pronounced and strongly expressed.

Fig.1. Increased aggression rate in females and males.

The open field test is a straight-forward test to investigate activity, anxiety-related behavior, and exploratory behavior in rodents. According to the crossed lines, which is an indicator of locomotor activity, the decrease in activity was more noticeable in females than in male rats (Fig. 2). The number of entries in the center shows the level of emotional tension. Female rats showed much lower levels of emotional tension than male rats, which exhibited higher levels of anxiety (Fig. 3).

Fig. 2. Number of line crossing in open field.

In addition, grooming duration and frequency were increased by 20-30% in animals of both sexes. However, defecation rate was not significantly different from that of control animals.

The Elevated Plus Maze (EPM) test is used to assess anxiety-related behavior in rodent models of CNS disorders. The preference for being in open arms over closed arms (expressed as either as a percentage of entries and/or a percentage of time spent in the open arms) is calculated to measure anxiety-like behavior.

Male rats showed a higher anxiety-like response to manganese as evidenced by: lower number of entries into the open arm of the EPM and less time spent into open arms. It should be noted that manganese exposed male rats spent statistically significant more time ($P < 0.05$) in the closed arms than control rats. On the contrary, female rats spent more time in open arms compared to control rats, although this difference was not statistically significant (Fig.4).

As for the evaluation of the learning process in the multi-branched maze, manganese exposed rats lagged behind control animals in maze performance, but these impairments were different in female and male rats. Male rats made more mistakes in the learning process than control ones, and at the end of the session they could not learn to pass the maze without errors (Fig. 5, Fig. 6). The female rats in the last days of the labyrinthine session almost reached the same rate as the control animals, but there was a difference in the time required to cross the maze (Fig.7, Fig. 8). They needed about twice as much time to complete the task as control ones. If control rats needed less than 20 seconds at the end of the session, manganese exposed rats needed more than 40 seconds. These values were maintained for 2 months since the memory test was performed.

Fig. 3. Number of entries in Center of open field.

Fig. 4. Results of the Elevated Plus Maze.

Manganese ion levels were estimated by atomic absorption spectrometry. Specimens were carbonized by moist mineralization. After measuring the optical densities of a sample and standard solutions of different concentrations, manganese contents were read from the resulting curve. These data are given in the tables (Table 1 and Table 2).

Based on the obtained data, it is obvious that highest accumulation of manganese ions was in the hippocampus and the neocortex. This applies to both female and male rats. To evaluate morphological alterations - we counted the number of neurons in these areas. Cell counting in hippocampal CA1, CA3 areas, Dentate Gyrus, prefrontal and motor cortex was conducted. Statistically significant decrease of neurons was noticeable in the CA3 field, but this only applied to male rats. A statistically significant decrease was also observed in Dentate Gyrus in both female and male rats. As for the neocortex, there was a decrease in both - prefrontal and locomotor cortex, but this decrease was not statistically significant.

Duration of maze performance

Fig. 5. Duration of multi-branched maze performance in male rats.

Fig. 6. Number of errors in multi-branched maze made by male rats.

Fig. 7. Duration of multi-branched maze performance in female rats.

Number of errors

Fig. 8. Number of errors in multi-branched maze made by female rats.

Table 1

Manganese ion accumulation in different brain regions of male rats, * $p < 0.05$.

Brain region	Control	MnCl ₂ · 4H ₂ O
Neocortex	0.028±0.001	0.083±0.037*
Striatum and Diencephalon	0.051±0.025	0.063±0.005
Mesencephalon and	0.029±0.005	0.036±0.002
Medulla Oblongata		
Hippocampus	0.077±0.002	0.420±0.021*

Table 2

Manganese ion accumulation in different brain regions of female rats, *p<0.05.

Brain region	Control	MnCl ₂ · 4H ₂ O
Neocortex	0.030±0.001	0.081±0.025*
Striatum and Diencephalon	0.049±0.025	0.061±0.005
Mesencephalon and Medulla Oblongata	0.030±0.005	0.033±0.001

4. Discussion

The results of the present study indicate that manganese compounds cause different anxiety-like responses in male vs. female rats. Thus, male rats appear to be more responsive and show a greater degree of anxiety-like behavior following the exposure to manganese ions. This anxiety like behavior was reflected in lower number of entries into the open-arm maze of the EPM, lower number of entries into central zone of OF. Avoidance of entry into the open arm of EPM or central zone of OF are common indication of an anxiety response. Our findings confirm the existence of sex-dependent differences following the exposure to manganese. Numerous studies have confirmed sex or sex-related differences in the expression of emotional behavior. For Parkinson's disease, gender differences are described in terms of disease spread, age of onset, and progression. It is known that the symptoms of the disease are less pronounced in women. But in the study of manganese neurotoxicity little attention has been paid to this issue. This has not been the main focus in the field of manganese toxicology. It is well known that studies on animal models are often conducted to study Parkinson's disease, and these studies have shown that gender differences play an important role in the development of the disease. In particular, estrogen has been found to play a protective role in neuropathology and behavior. Survival of dopamine neurons after exposure to dopamine neurotoxic agents used in animal models of Parkinson's disease depends on the gender. For example, a study examining the gender impact of 6-hydroxydopamine (6-OHDA) lesions on behavior and neuropathology found that male rats were more sensitive to this toxic substance than female rats. Our studies also showed that male rats

were more sensitive to manganese ions than female rats. Interestingly, male rats were more prone to depression, but in some situations, they were more aggressive than female rats.

In addition, it is known that cases of depressive disorder, anxiety, inability to suppress fear are more common in women than in men. Two-thirds of patients with depressive or stress-related disorders are women. However, preclinical studies related to anxiety rates indicate a higher sensitivity to stress stimuli in males than in females. Experiments on rats have revealed a number of cases that adult female rats spend more time in the open arms of the cross-maze than adult male rats, which also occurred during our experiment. Thus, the difficulty is due to the fact that in many cases the results are contradictory and there is no clear conclusion about the direction of development of mental disorder.

It should also be noted that according to some data, sex influences the differences in the distribution of Mn in the body [9]. Women have a high prevalence of Mn levels in different countries, which may be related to the better food absorption. In our experiments we didn't find any noticeable differences between the levels of manganese ion accumulation in brain regions.

Based on the data obtained by our experiments, the prominent decrease in the amount of neurons was detected in the brain regions of male rats. While in females, neuronal loss was mostly observed among dopaminergic neurons, as females expressed significant impairments in locomotor activity. Scientific data indicates that Manganese ions target dopaminergic neurons, especially in the striatum and cause alterations in their morphology. The same scenario (damaged dopaminergic neurons) is characteristic to Parkinson's disease.

5. Conclusions

Intoxication with manganese compounds has a significant impact on the aggressive behavior and emotional state of individuals. Aggressive behavior and alterations in the emotional state is expressed in both male and female rats. Decreased locomotor activity is observed in female rats. Rats intoxicated with manganese ions lag behind control animals in learning ability. Disorders in the learning process are more pronounced in male individuals. Accumulation of manganese ions in areas of the brain is particularly pronounced in the hippocampus and cerebral cortex. Changes in the number of neurons in the hippocampus were observed in the CA3 field and the dentate gyrus.

Acknowledgments

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VARIATION OF INDUCED PURE TONE AUDIOMETRY OF HIDDEN HEARING LOSS IN MUSIC PLAYER USERS

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Abstract

Hearing acuity has been estimated in 277 university students of Georgia. 150 from, were regular music player employers while remainder 127 have been not utilized habitually any local music device and constituted thus the control group. Ages of individuals in both sample collections fell in the range of 18-25 years. Auditory thresholds were measured monaurally by the pure tone audiometer within the band of 1-12-kHz frequencies. The overall time of the player service was different among individual admirers while only a restricted number used to listen to the music more than 8 hours per day. At the principal speech frequency link, 1-6 kHz, the thresholds in player music consumers did not differ from those in non-consumers. At 8 and, especially, 12 kHz, however, the player music fans possessed greater thresholds. High-frequency hearing disorders did not display any persistent dependence upon everyday music listening lengths. The process of hearing disturbances along with a group-systematic character seemed thus to own an individual-sensitive quality also. When analyzing the personal data, the gender bearing trend was revealed furthermore: high-frequency threshold elevations appeared in somewhat greater rate in female than in male consumers. Systematic audiometrical inspection of personal music player followers is recommended for an in-time disclosure of a hearing disorder and an immediate start then of corresponding treatment and preventive means. The hearing testing has to include high tone frequencies, 12 kHz, e.g.

Keywords: personal music player users; acoustic trauma; frequencies; gender factor; prevention of hearing loss

1. Introduction

Music players are rather popular in the world around. The maximal sound intensity in players reaches 100-120 dB [1,2]. The users mostly use the devices in the noisy environments: when walking through the streets, when

transporting over, etc. In such situations the outer noise level approximates conventionally to 90 dB [3].

To follow the applied melody, the music intensity in players should thus exceed 90 dB that appearing harmful for delicate inner-ear structures [4,5].

2. Materials and Methods

The influence of the player music on the hearing function has been estimated in the present study. 277 students of the higher education establishments participated in the project. The age of inspected individuals fell within the range of 18-25 years. 174 from the tested subjects were females and 103 were males. 150 participants, 141 females and 49 males, were music player fans while 127 individuals, 73 females and 54 males, were apart from the regular music player users and constituted thus the control sample. Potential participants of the research underwent initially otoscopy. If finding cerumen or any outer- and middle-ear pathology, the subject was not included in the study. Individuals filled then the particular questionnaire. The subjects were excluded from the sample if indicating the history of auditory trauma, and/or of the use of ototoxic drugs, and/or of a family history of a hearing loss at early ages. Special attention was given to the duration of the music player usage: how many years, how many days, and how many hours per day are involved the participants in music habits.

Hearing thresholds were determined in a soundproof chamber. The pure-tone audiometry was conducted by GCI-16 Audiometer. Hearing acuity indices were determined monaurally at 1-, 2-, 3-, 4-, 6-, 8-, and 12-kHz frequencies.

The program IBM SPSS Statistics 20 was applied for the quantitative processing of obtained results. The primary data analyses, e.g. revealing of ratios and estimation of mean values, were descriptive. The comparison of the test vs. the control intergroup categorical variables was performed utilizing the Pirson Chi-Square Test.

3. Results

Auditory threshold values of music player users and non-users were estimated at 1-12-kHz frequency band (Fig. 1). No difference was found at 1-6-kHz frequencies. At higher frequencies, 8 and 12 kHz, the thresholds in peri aural player music users regularly exceeded those in non-users (Fig. 1 and Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Auditory thresholds in personal music player users and non-users at 1-12-kHz frequencies.

Fig. 2. Incidences auditory threshold augmentation at 8- and 12 kHz frequencies of music player users and non-users.

At 8 kHz the mean difference approximated to 2 dB while at 12 kHz to 4 dB. The latter disparity was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). The systematic usage of player music can lead thus to high-frequency hearing impairments. From the overall number of 277 inspected individuals, the impaired hearing at 12-kHz frequency was the case in 101. From those, 80 subjects belonged to the test subgroup of the music player fans while 21 only to the control one, 79.2% and 20.8%, respectively ($p < 0.001$). Within the inspected generation, the increase in auditory thresholds at high sound frequencies did not display any dependence upon the age of music player users: the incidences of high-frequency hearing worsening in age groups of

18-20 and 21-25 years appeared rather similar.

From the overall number of the 80 music player users, demonstrating an increase in auditory thresholds at 12-kHz frequency, in 54 individuals it occurred unilaterally while in 26 bilaterally. The threshold augmentation appeared thus twice as much unilaterally than bilaterally: 67.3% and 32.7% of cases, respectively. The hearing threshold augmentation at high auditory frequencies failed to correlate with duration of music player listening. The threshold augmentation at 12-kHz frequency was detected somewhat more frequently in users involved in music player more than 6 hours per day, 54.2%. On the other hand, the impairment incidence was greater in individuals rarely, 1-2 hours, than more intensively, 3-6 hours, being engaged in everyday music: 48.6% and 40.7%, respectively.

The incidences of auditory threshold augmentation at high auditory frequencies in the control subgroup were lower in females than in males: 12% and 22%, respectively. In the test subgroup, on the opposite, the rate of high-frequency impairment in females exceeded that in males: 55% and 49%, respectively. The ears of females appeared thus more sensitive to the music player effects than those of males.

4. Conclusions

The following conclusions were reached considering the results of the study:

(1) At conventional speech frequencies the hearing thresholds in music player users are within the normal limits and statistically are not differed thus from those in non-users.

(2) The hearing thresholds in music player users are increased at high sound frequencies, at 8 and 12 kHz, in particular.

(3) Augmentation of hearing thresholds in music player users at high auditory frequencies are not correlated with everyday lengths of the player usage and bear thus more individual-personal rather than systemic-group character.

(4) The effects of music listening on a hearing function possess gender specific character: high-frequency hearing loss due to systematic music listening has more regular character in female than in male music player users.

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IN-VIVO DOSIMETRY AND RADIATION CATARACT IN BRACHYTHERAPY PATIENTS

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Abstract

Radiation cataract causes partial opacity or cloudiness in the crystalline lens and results from damaged cells covering the posterior surface of the lens. Symptoms can appear as early as one or two years following high-dose exposure and many years after exposure to lower doses. Cataract is a frequent complication of brachytherapy when treated melanoma with localization on the face, nearby with eyes. Radiation Protection and International Commission on Radiological Protection assumptions that a radiation dose of at least 2 Gy is associated with increased cataract risk. For the protection of eyes is used shielding with lead plates in many clinics in the world in pair with in-vivo dosimetry for monitoring. There are several technologies for in-vivo dosimetry. One of them is OSL (optically stimulated luminescence) technology, which is practiced at at Fridon Todua Named Research Institute of Clinical Medicine, Tbilisi, Georgia. For in-vivo dosimetry is used special nanoDot dosimeters. They are designed for use in single point radiation assessment applications. Due to theirs small size, they do not affect the quality of the treatment. The nanoDot dosimeters are wireless and radiolucent. Brachytherapy in Fridon Todua Named Research Institute of Clinical Medicine has been introduced since 2018. During the period 2018-2020, in-vivo dosimetry was carried out

in patients with melanoma located on the face in 689 fractions of radiation therapy, including 236 in 2018, 201 in 2019 and 252 in 2020. According to the results of dosimetry monitoring, the risk of cataract occurrence was revealed in only 5 patients (22.7%) in 2018, 2 patients (12.5%) in 2019 and 4 patients (14.8%) in 2020. This risk has been minimized by a dose correction within the limits to allow successful treatment.

Keywords: brachytherapy; in-vivo dosimetry; radiation; cataract; patients

1. Introduction

Radiation cataract causes partial opacity or cloudiness in the crystalline lens and results from damaged cells covering the posterior surface of the lens. Symptoms can appear as early as one or two years following high-dose exposure and many years after exposure to lower doses. The excess cataracts seen are of the types generally associated with radiation: posterior subcapsular and cortical cataracts. Figure 1 shows the relation between radiation dose and cortical opacity of lens.

Figure 2 describes how lens opacity is caused by radiation. There is a transparent layer of epithelial cells on the interior frontal side of the capsule that covers the lens. This layer maintains the function of the lens by slowly growing toward the center, achieved through cell division at the periphery (called the equator) of the lens. Because radiation is especially harmful to dividing cells, exposed cells at the equator are most prone to damage. For unknown reasons, damaged cells move toward the rear of the lens before converging on the center. Such cells prevent light from traveling straight forward, resulting in opacity [1].

Fig. 1. Cortical opacity of lens and radiation dose.

Fig. 2. Lens opacity at the posterior subcapsular region caused by radiation (from Effects of A-bomb Radiation on the Human Body, ed by HICARE in 1991, courtesy of Bunkodo Co., Ltd., Tokyo).

Cataract is a frequent complication of brachytherapy when treated melanoma with localization on the face, nearby with eyes. Radiation Protection and International Commission on Radiological Protection assumptions that a radiation dose of at least 2 Gy is associated with increased cataract risk.

For the protection of eyes is used shielding with lead plates in many clinics in the world in pair with in-vivo dosimetry for monitoring. This is considered to be the best method control of radiation cataract when the location of melanoma is on face, nearby the eyes [2].

There are several technologies for in-vivo dosimetry. One of them is OSL (optically stimulated luminescence) dosimetry practiced at Acad. Fridon Todua Medical Center, Tbilisi, Georgia, where we do our research. For OSL dosimetry we use special nanoDot dosimeters.

2. Materials and Methods

In physics, optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) is a method for measuring doses from ionizing radiation. Optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) technology is a dramatic breakthrough in radiation detection. The key to the success of OSL technology is the detector material, aluminum oxide crystals (Al₂O₃:C).

Aluminum oxide crystals were first developed as a supersensitive thermoluminescence detector (TLD), but its real advantages were recognized

only after advances in optical technology. With OSL, the amount of radiation exposure is measured by stimulating the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3:\text{C}$ material with green light from either a laser or light emitting diode source. Aluminum oxide crystals are manufactured using a proprietary crystal growth process. High purity aluminum oxide is melted at high temperatures and recrystallized in order to introduce dopants and oxygen vacancies. The dopants and vacancies dictate the OSL properties of the radiation sensitive $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3:\text{C}$. Custom designed furnaces are used to precisely control the process necessary to produce aluminum oxide crystals for radiation measurement.

The amount of light released during optional stimulation is directly proportional to the radiation dose and the intensity of stimulation light. The first OSL dosimeter based on aluminum oxide was first introduced in 1996 to a limited market with the official LUXEL® technology launched in 1998. Today, OSL technology dosimetry is very popular.

As for OSL nanoDot dosimeters, they are designed for use in single point radiation assessment applications, and are engineered to be read them out. The nanoDot dosimeter can be used in medical applications, in vivo dosimetry, and researches. Due to their small size (square ABC plastic, 10.0X10.0 mm, 2.0 mm thick), they do not affect the quality of the treatment. The nanoDot dosimeters are wireless and radiolucent.

The nanoDot dosimeters can be used without buildup to make surface dose measurement. In radiation oncology, they can be used with buildup to make measurements at various depths, which is what we use in in-vivo dosimetry for brachytherapy patients when treated melanoma with localization on the face, nearby with eyes [3].

The OSL nanoDot dosimeter has got the following technical specifications: dose operating range is 10 μGy to $>100\text{Gy}$ for general applications; lower Limit of Detection is 0.1 mGy; useful Energy Range is from 5 keV to 20 MeV; energy Dependence is follow - Accurate within $\pm 10\%$ over diagnostic energy range 70-140 kvP, but within $\pm 5\%$ for photons and electrons from 5 MeV-20MeV; accuracy (total uncertainly - single measurement) is $\pm 10\%$ with standard nanoDot and $\pm 5.5\%$ with screened nanoDot; precision is $\pm 5\%$, $k=2$ for both standard and screened nanoDot.

Key features and advantages of nanoDot dosimeters are the following: nondestructive readout; allows for reanalysis and reuse; accurate measurement across a wide dose range; no need to anneal every time the dosimeter will be exposed to ionizing radiation; element correction factors are not required; minimal fading; dosimeter archiving is possible; dosimeters are durable (shock resistant; moisture resistant; high temperature tolerance); no required heating parameters and gas to maintain; effective replacement for

older radiation measurement technology (e.g., TLD) [4].

Brachytherapy in Acad. Fridon Todua Medical Center has been introduced since 2018. During the period 2018-2020, OSL dosimetry was carried out in patients with melanoma located on the face in 689 fractions of radiation therapy, including 236 fractions in 2018, 201 fractions in 2019 and 252 fractions in 2020. These results are shown at the table 1.

For this period (2018-2020) the risk of cataract occurrence was revealed in only 11 patients, including 5 patients (22.7%) in 2018, 2 patients (12.5%) in 2019 and 4 patients (14.8%) in 2020. At the table 2 it is done the data for 10 patients for each year with highest doses. For every patient it was used shielding with lead plates.

From the table 2 it is clear that in 2018 the highest dose was 3,53 Gy, in 2019 2.12 Gy, but in 2020 2.81 Gy. In all these cases the risk has been minimized due to dose correction within the treatment interest

Table 1
Number of brachytherapy fractions and patients with risk of cataract occurrence (2018-2020)

Number of brachytherapy fractions and patients with risk of cataract occurrence	2018	2019	2020
Number of brachytherapy fractions	236	201	252
Number of brachytherapy patients with risk of cataract occurrence	5	2	4

Table 2
Summary doses of brachytherapy patients (2018-2020)

Summary doses (Gy)	2018	2019	2020
Summary doses of Brachytherapy patients (Gy)	3.53	2.07	1.48
	3.07	1.54	2.81
	1.78	2.12	1.44
	1.78	0.35	1.52
	1.47	1.22	2.07
	1.78	0.73	0.91
	2.39	1.04	2.03
	2.62	1.45	0.95
	1.86	0.33	2.05
	2.16	0.22	0.95

3. Results

During the period 2018-2020, at Acad. Fridon Todua Medical Center, Tbilisi, Georgia, in-vivo dosimetry was carried out in patients with melanoma located on the face in 689 fractions of radiation therapy, including 236 in 2018, 201 in 2019 and 252 in 2020.

According to the results of dosimetry monitoring, the risk of cataract occurrence was revealed in only 5 patients (22.7%) in 2018, 2 patients (12.5%) in 2019 and 4 patients (14.8%) in 2020. This risk has been minimized by a dose correction within the limits to allow successful treatment.

4. Discussion

Using OSL technology in-vivo dosimetry is very important for monitoring in brachytherapy patients. This is effective way in pair with shielding with lead plates for radiation cataract prevention when the location of melanoma is on face, nearby the eyes.

For future I plan to continue studying doses of brachytherapy patients with melanoma localized on the face, nearby with eyes, on the base of Fridon Todua Named Research Institute of Clinical Medicine, Tbilisi, Georgia.

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STUDY OF COGNITIVE PARAMETERS IN THE POST-RADIATION PERIOD IN WHITE MICE

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Abstract

The aim of the study was to establish the dependence of memory formation processes and learning ability in gamma-irradiated white mice on the age and period after irradiation. The 1.5 year old male mice (*Mus musculus*) were used in the study. Mice whole-body irradiation with ¹³⁷Cs was performed at a dose of 5 Gy with a “Gamma-capsule-2”. Spatial learning and memory formation were estimated in the elevated-type multi-way maze. Experiments were carried out after 48 hours and 30 days of irradiation for seven days (five trials each day). The number of errors (deviations from optimal trajectory) and total time for crossing the maze were calculated. The results of the study indicate that ionizing irradiation with total dose 5 Gy causes no significant spatial memory and behavior changes and aged-mice are more radio-resistant. Age-related radioresistance plays a major role in the early stage of post-radiation recovery. Though, the late radiation cognitive impairment marked by decreased verbal memory, spatial memory and attention has especially acute manifestation in young animals. These data match the literature data on the age dependence of radiation-induced cognitive dysfunction.

Keywords: Ionizing radiation; cognitive parameters; spatial learning; elevated plus maze

1. Introduction

Ionizing radiation has multiple effects on brain functioning, behavior, and cognitive function. These changes are largely dependent on the radiation dose. Studies revealed that ionizing radiation affects the functions of the

central nervous system what results in behavior and memory changes; these changes occur as a result of a direct effect of irradiation of the central nervous system and also indirect, as a result of response to irradiation of other organ systems [1]. The central nervous system is considered a radiosensitive system, and the degree of its dysfunction can be evaluated by electrophysiological, biochemical, and behavioral parameters. Impairments of these parameters can be observed after local, also total irradiation of the whole body [2].

Nowadays, there is increasing evidence literature date that the response of the central nervous system to radiation is a continuous and interactive process. Particular attention is paid to apoptotic cell (neuronal) death, as well as, mechanisms of cells' damage and death induced by secondary injury [3].

Recent studies revealed cranial radiation therapy's impact on a wide range of brain functions resulting in cognitive and memory deficiency. Radiation-induced alterations develop with a dose-volume-dependent severity. After irradiation of the brain, detrimental effects develop, acute, early delayed, and late injuries are observed. High doses of ionizing radiation induce reactive gliosis, white matter necrosis, vascular abnormalities, which are irreversible and result in clinical symptoms [4]. Low doses can also induce a wide array of cognitive dysfunctions without any significant morphological changes [5].

Dysfunction of the central nervous system is manifested after a certain interval of time (months or years) of radiation exposure. Cognitive impairment is revealed in various degrees of learning difficulties, behavior changes, and memory deficits [6].

The presence of cognitive disorders after exposure to high dose irradiation have a connection to the hippocampus glial cells and proliferating progenitor cells in the subgranular zone of the dentate gyrus. This region is especially sensitive to ionizing radiation [7]. Doses of ionizing radiation above 1 Gy decreased the number of neural progenitor cells, which results in the arrested cell cycle, induces oxidative stress [8], and manifests as a cognitive disability, memory, and learning dysfunctions [9].

The aim of the study was to establish the dependence of memory processes and learning ability in gamma-irradiated white mice on the age and period after irradiation.

2. Materials and Methods

The experimental protocol was in accordance with the guidelines for care and use of laboratory animals as adopted by the Ethics Committee of the Tbilisi State Medical University (TSMU).

2.1. Animal care and maintenance

1,5 year-old male mice (*Mus musculus*), were obtained from the Vivarium of Tbilisi State Medical University. They were housed in animal cages, with room temperature maintained at 20⁰-22⁰C, relative humidity of 50-70%, and an airflow rate of 15 exchange/h. Also, a time-controlled system provided 08:00-20:00 h light and 20:00-08:00 h dark cycles. All mice were given a standard rodent chow diet and water from sanitized bottle fitted with stopper and sipper tubes.

2.2. Experimental design

After acclimatization for a week to laboratory conditions, the mice were divided into two different groups. The I control group of 1.5-old not irradiated mice, II experimental group - 1.5-old irradiated mice. Mice whole-body irradiation with ¹³⁷Cs was performed at a dose rate of 1,1Gy/min for the total dose of 5 Gy with a “Gamma-capsule-2” (group II).

Spatial learning and formation of memory were estimated in the elevated-type multi-way maze.

The maze consists of 10 platforms (40x10 cm) fixed at a height of 25 cm. The motivation for movement along the maze under test conditions was to go back in the box-nest fixed at the end of the maze.

Experiments were carried out after 48 hours and 30 days of irradiation for seven days (five trials each day). Animals were placed in the start point facing the pathway of the maze. The familiarization session consisted of free exploration of the start and familiar arms for 10 min. On the first day, the experimenter helped the animal to find the optimal way leading to box-nest. The number of errors (deviations from optimal trajectory) and total time for crossing the maze were calculated. Analysis of the obtained numerical data allowed us to estimate the dynamics of the learning process. Free passing in the labyrinth during 10-15 sec and the achievement of automated behavior was considered as a criterion of the complete learning process.

All experimental areas were wiped with 20% ethanol after each trial. All behavioral experiments were conducted during the light cycle after two hours of acclimation.

2.3. Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis of data was carried out using the “Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) for Windows (SPSS version 11.0). Data were reported as mean ± SD. A significant level of 0.05 was chosen to assess the statistical significance.

3. Results

Monitoring of spatial learning process of two animal groups in the elevated maze showed that animals of group I (control group of 1.5 year old mice) when placed in the maze for the first time, needed the help of the experimenter only in two trials of the first testing day. Later they independently opened up the new environment and demonstrated research activity. In animals of the I control group the average number of errors and mean time for crossing the maze, accordingly, was equal to 3 and 2 (± 0.5) min. Later animals independently opened up the new environment and the number of errors decreased and on the 6th and 7th days, mice found the shortest way leading to target and spent an average of 20 sec. Animals of the experimental II group showed decreased number of errors and on the 5th day of the experiment Improvement of the learning process and the total average time: mice reached the target-nest in 40 sec and the number of errors was the same compared to the control group. On the next 2-4th days the average number of errors decreased and the total average time became less than 3 minutes. Improvement of the learning process and the total average time needed for crossing the maze, determined by the middle part of the maze, significantly increased the rate of path recognition. Though on 6-7th days of the experiment the average number of errors and time gradually increased (Fig. 1). The same results were obtained after one month of irradiation (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Effect of gamma-radiation on the cognitive parameters of 1,5-year old white mice after 48 hours of irradiation (during the 1-week period). A - Average number of errors in control and experimental mice (groups I, II); B- Average time to cross the maze (min) in control and experimental mice (groups I, II).

Fig. 2. Effect of gamma-radiation on the cognitive parameters of 1,5-year old white mice after one month of irradiation (during the 1-week period). A - Average number of errors in control and experimental mice (groups I, II); B- Average time to cross the maze (min) in control and experimental mice (groups I, II).

4. Discussion

The results of the study indicate that ionizing irradiation with total dose 5 Gy in the old (1,5-year-old) mice delaying effect of the radiation on the spatial learning process was insignificant. As seems from the results of our experiment, aged animals turned out to be more radioresistant. These data match the literature data on the age dependence of radiation-induced cognitive dysfunction; epidemiological studies revealed that the risk for cognitive dysfunctions is higher during prenatal and childhood irradiation [10].

5. Conclusion

Using a laboratory white mouse model, the results of the study indicate that that ionizing radiation exposure causes insignificant spatial memory and behavior changes in aged animals – aged mice turned out to be more radio-resistant. Age-related radioresistance plays an especially major role in the early stage of post-radiation recovery. Though, the late radiation aging effect formation is especially pronounced in young animals.

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COGNITIVE FUNCTIONS IN GEORGIAN CHILDREN WITH DYSLEXIA AND COMORBID DYSLEXIA AND ATTENTION-DEFICIT/HYPERACTIVITY DISORDER

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Abstract

In spite of the fact that dyslexia and Attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) are highly comorbid, less studies have investigated cognitive functions during co-occurring of those disorders. Here we studied such cognitive abilities as attention, memory, and executive functions in children with dyslexia and comorbid dyslexia/ADHD. Three groups of age- and IQ-match children participated in our study: children with dyslexia (group 1), children having ADHD and dyslexia together (group 2) and typically developing children (group 3). All participants performed the visual search tasks, visual working memory task (visual N-back task) and executive function task (WCST). We found that children with comorbid dyslexia/ADHD showed a strong impairment in performance of search tasks while children with dyslexia showed significant worse performance than typically developing children only when task condition was more complex. However, both dyslexia and dyslexia/ADHD groups showed deficits in visual working memory compare to typically developing children. As for executive function task, only children with comorbid dyslexia/ADHD showed a significant worse performance compare to typically developing children. Here, we concluded that visual attention and visual working memory are impaired in children with either dyslexia or comorbid dyslexia/ADHD and these impairments are stronger in dyslexia/ADHD group. Yet, deficits in executive functions are more specific for children with comorbid dyslexia/ADHD.

Keywords: dyslexia; ADHD; attention; executive functions

1. Introduction

Neurodevelopmental disorders are group of conditions that are caused by impairment in learning, language, or behavior areas. These disorders begin during the developmental period, appear in childhood and some of them even are preserved in adults. Examples of neurodevelopmental disorders in children include attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), learning disabilities

(including dyslexia, dyscalculia, dysgraphia etc.), autism spectrum disorder, intellectual disability, cerebral palsy, and many others. Approximately 20% of school age children worldwide are affected by neurodevelopmental disorders. Among these conditions, ADHD and learning disabilities had the greatest prevalence and one of the common types of learning disabilities - dyslexia is the dominant. Moreover, many children have more than one of these conditions together.

Dyslexia is reading disorder characterized by difficulties with accurate and/or fluent word recognition as well as poor spelling and decoding abilities. There are many theories proposed to explain mechanisms of reading difficulties and two of them are dominant: deficits in phonological processing and deficits in visual information processing that involved those brain areas where integration of sensory inputs happen, and that are responsible for word analysis and for attention [1]. ADHD is characterized by difficulties with attention, hyperactivity and impulsiveness. Core deficits in ADHD are related to cognitive disabilities that are explained by evidences about atypical neurophysiological patterns in fronto-striatal, fronto-parietal, and sensory circuits in children and adults with ADHD [2].

It is evidenced that ADHD often co-occurs in combination with dyslexia [3]. These two disorders apparently have same genetic basis and share some biological and cognitive dysfunctions [4]. Still, the etiology of comorbidity of the two disorders stays unclear.

Cognitive functions including such domains as attention, memory and executive functions were subject of intensive investigation in children with neurodevelopmental disorders. However, evidences from those studies are controversial and sometimes even conflicting. For example, Varvara and colleagues [5] have shown that children with dyslexia compare to their age-match controls show deficits in visual-spatial attention and visual short-term memory. While Moura and colleagues [6] have shown deficits in verbal but not in visual memory. Stins and colleagues [7] investigated sustained attention and executive functions in children with ADHD and showed overall performance deficit for children with ADHD but no difference in reaction times compare to control group children. On the other hand, the evidence shows that dyslexia and ADHD both have cognitive deficits in processing the speed [4].

Despite the facts that both ADHD and dyslexia are quite popular disabilities and attract attention of researchers from different scientific backgrounds, there are still controversies whether cognitive functions are affected in children with these disorders or not and even less is know when the two disorders co-occur.

In the present study we aimed to investigate the cognitive such functions as attention, visual working memory and executive function in Georgian children with dyslexia and with comorbidity of dyslexia and Attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder. To the end, we used the visual search task, visual n-back task and Wisconsin Card Sorting Test (WCST), and compared performance between three groups: children with dyslexia (group 1), children having ADHD and dyslexia together (group 2) and typically developing children (group 3).

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Participants

Sixty age and IQ match children (aged between 8 and 10 years) participated in the study. Participants were divided into three groups: group 1 - children with dyslexia (n=24, 18 boys) group 2 - children with ADHD+dyslexia (n=12, all boys) and group 3 - typically developing children (n=24, 18 boys) (see details in table 1). The diagnosis of dyslexia and ADHD were made by a specialist of the Multi-Disciplinary Group of the Ministry of Education, Science, Culture, And Sport of Georgia. The tests used for diagnosis were cross -cultural adapted and normalized on Georgian population, including Wide Range Achievement Test (WRAT-4), test for nonverbal intelligence (TONI-4), the Woodcock-Johnson Tests (WJ III). However, we had not direct access to individual screening data and therefor did not report the dyslexia and ADHD screening details here. General intelligence of all participants was evaluated by officially standardized tests TONI-4 (fourth edition) and all included participants had normal IQ to their age (table 1).

The study was performed in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and was approved by the local Bioethics Committee of Ivane Beritashvili Center of Experimental Biomedicine (10 / 30.01.2017). Parents of all participants gave their informed consent prior to starting the experiment. All participants received compensation for participation.

2.2. Stimuli and Procedure

Children were tested individually in a quiet experimental room. Data were collected on a Windows PC with LCD display (screen resolution 1280x800 pixels). We used The Psychology Experiment Building Language (PEBL) program for running experiments [14].

The following tests were used:

2.3. Visual Search Task

The test provides a good measure of visual selective attention. The target stimulus is green horizontal line presented on task of a participant was to

find and respond on presence of target stimulus - a within distractors (red and green lines). The display elements were presented on a uniform grey background. The search display consisted of 4, 9 or 16 elements and the numbers of elements were changed trial-by-trial. Participants were instructed to search and respond as soon as possible by giving answer 'yes' if a target was presented and press the green button in right hand and 'no' if target was not presented and press the red button with left hand. At the beginning of a trial, a central fixation dot appeared for 700 milliseconds (msec), then the fixation dot was replaced by the stimulus field which was presented for 200 msec. Participants performed a single block of 120 trials in which there were equal numbers of target present and target absent trials. The reaction times (RT) and response accuracies were recorded and analyzed.

2.4. Visual n-back task

The N-back task is a continuous performance task that is commonly used to assess working memory. In this task 'n' refers on how many previous stimuli must be remembered. 1-back and 2-back conditions were used. Participants are presented the sequence of visual stimuli (pictures of different objects like tree, umbrella, ball etc.,) and during 1-back condition they responded whether current stimulus matched with the previous one or not by pressing right and left arrow on the computer keyboard respectively; during 2-back condition participants indicated whether current stimulus matched with the stimulus before the previous one. The Stimuli were presented in pseudorandom sequences in a fixed central location on a computer screen for 500 msec duration with 2500 ms interstimulus interval. Both correct responses and false alarms were recorded and analyzed.

2.5. Wisconsin Card Sorting Test (WCST)

This test is used to evaluate the executive functions. WCST contains 128 cards that differ from each other in three dimensions (color, amount and shape) and a participant need to sort cards according to one of the dimensions. In every 10 trials sorting dimension is changed and a participant is required to change and adjust to new sorting strategies. Performance is evaluated according to several outcomes, e.g., perseverative errors (cognitive flexibility), non-perseverative errors (distractibility), number of trials to complete the first category (conceptual ability), and failure to maintain set (working memory) and so on.

2.6. Data analysis

For all three groups we calculated reaction times and overall accuracy. Reaction times (RT) faster than 150 msec were categorized as 'fast guesses' and slower than 3500 msec as 'too slow' for that age of children and were excluded from the analysis. Both of these categories occurred in <1% of

trials. RTs and accuracies were analyzed with analysis of variance (ANOVA) in SPSS statistical program (IBM corp., Version 20.0). Performance of tasks (accuracy) and RTs were compared between the groups.

3. Results

3.1. Visual Search Task

We calculated mean reaction times (RTs) and mean percentage of correct responses for each group. Figure 1 shows the mean RTs for each group. RTs are increased with number of distractors for all groups of participants, indicating that participants use serial search. RTs between groups were different and children of group 2 had longer RTs and children of group 3 had shorter RTs. An analysis of variance (one-way ANOVA) showed significant group effect for RTs on search displays with 4 and 9 elements, $F(2,30)=5.379$, $p=0.01$ and $F(2,30)=6.697$, $p=0.004$ respectively. No significant group effect was found for 16 element displays, $F(2,30)=2.388$, $p=0.109$. However, both dyslexia and dyslexia/AHDH groups showed significant worse performance than TD group for 16 element displays condition.

Figure 2 shows performance of search task. Mean performances varied across the different displays and groups, $F(2,30)=5.379$, $p=0.01$. Pair-wise comparison between the groups showed that for 4 and 9 elements search displays there were no significant differences between the performance of group 1 and group 2 ($p>0.05$) and group 1 and group 3 ($p>0.05$), but there was significant difference between the performance of group 2 and group 3 ($p<0.05$); for 16 elements search displays there were no significant differences between the performances of all groups ($p>0.05$).

3.2. Visual n-back task

The means of performances of 1-back and 2-back conditions for three groups are shown in Figure 3. Mean performances varied across the groups, $F(2,30)=4.246$, $p=0.024$. Pair-wise comparison between the groups showed that there was no significant difference between the performances of group 1 and group 2 ($p=0.299$) but performance of typically developing children was statistically different from both groups 1 and 2, $p=0.03$ and $p=0.018$ respectively. As for performance of 2-back condition, even there is difference in performance between the groups, there are no significant differences.

3.3. Wisconsin Card Sorting Test (WCST)

Results of WCST for all groups are shown in table 2. Paired-sample t-test showed no significant differences between group 1 and group 3 in all parameters measured by WCST ($p>0.05$), and significant differences between group 1 and group 2 and between group 2 and group 3 ($p<0.05$). These results

show that children having dyslexia and ADHD together have deficits in executive functions that might be related to more ADHD rather than dyslexia.

Fig. 1. Reaction time of visual search task. Y axis shows the RT in milliseconds.

Fig. 2. Performance of visual search task. Y axis shows the percentage of correct responses.

Fig. 3. Performance of visual n-back task

Table 1
Performance of WCST. Means and standard deviations are presented for each group.

Participants	Number of correct responses	Number of total errors	Number of perseverative Errors	Number of nonperseverative Errors	Conceptual Level Responses
Dyslexia	83(±13)	45(±12)	24(±10)	21(±13)	69(±14)
Dyslexia+ADHD	70(±14)	58(±14)	26(±15)	32(±18)	45(±18)
Controls	94(±9)	34(±11)	21(±7)	13(±6)	80(±10)

4. Discussion

In the present study we investigated cognitive functions in Georgian children with dyslexia and comorbid ADHD/dyslexia and compared the performance of these groups to age- and IQ- match typically developing children. This is the first attempt in Georgia to evaluate cognitive functions in Georgian children with neurodevelopmental disorders.

The visual search task was used to evaluate the state of attention. We analyzed reaction time and accuracy rates that are the most frequently

assessed dependent variables for visual search. Visual search task is well investigated for dyslexia but not that much for ADHD. Our results showed that reaction times increased with number of search elements on display for all three groups that indicates serial search strategy by all participants. Reaction time for participants of group 1 and group 2 were higher compare to group 3 children that is in accordance to the literature data that dyslexia and ADHD have delayed sensory processing and hence increased reaction time [4]. RTs for easier conditions (4 or 9 element search displays) showed group difference, however, when the task is more complex (16 elements on search display) there was no significant difference between RTs of different groups. Task accuracy (performance) results also showed the same tendency that when task is complex the performance is not significantly different for three groups.

Visual N-back task was used to evaluate visual working memory. Results of these tasks showed deficits in visual working memory for both groups of children with neurodevelopmental disorders. However, as soon as the task is more complex, such deficits are seen for typically developing children too, that could be explained by assumption that for the age of 8-10 years mechanisms of visual working memory is not fully developed.

Executive functions were tested using WCST that is a complex test requiring involvement of different cognitive capacities for successful performance and is very good tool for evaluation of executive functions in neurodevelopmental disorders. The results showed that children with neurodevelopmental disorders (groups 1 and 2) had worst performance compare to children of group 3. However, surprisingly the performance of children with dyslexia was not significantly different from the performance of children of group 3. These results indicate that children with dyslexia show fewer deficits in executive functions. Deteriorated executive functions in comorbid group of ADHD+dyslexia could be related to more ADHD mechanisms rather than dyslexia.

The limitation of the study is that we could not recruit and include in our study one more group of children having only ADHD. Because of that, we can only speculate regarding our results and future studies including ADHD group would need to confirm our finding.

5. Conclusions

In conclusion, we found that in children with dyslexia and comorbid dyslexia/ADHD both visual attention and visual working memory are deteriorated. However, these deteriorations are stronger in children with comorbid

dyslexia/ADHD. Yet there is clear deficiency of executive functions only in children with comorbid dyslexia/ADHD.

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NEW APPROACH OF MEDICAL SERVICES

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Abstract

The current problems are this pre-pandemic reform phase involved many changes, mainly involving regulation, funding, recruitment/ training/ retraining/ mastering. The development and refinement of healthcare, introduction of complex measures for betterment allow to maintain and continuous improvement of the health of the whole community. We conducted an original study that focused on health care quality control research. In such an important and ongoing process, there is a list of problems that need to be addressed by consolidating specialists in many areas. Clinical and economic analysis of the activities of a particular doctor and nurse provides for the following types of management accounting: analysis of the volume of medical care and financial costs at each stage of medical care; elimination of processes that do not add value; making managerial decisions to improve the system for the provision of polyclinic care; reducing the variability of the processes. Systematization, analyzation and summarizing this date are very important for improvement healthcare in Georgia and other countries in the world.

Keywords: quality indicators; continuous medical training system; patient safety

1. Introduction

In the world, the pandemic caused by COVID-19, have changed the current healthcare system. The pre-pandemic reform phase involved many changes, mainly involving regulation, funding, recruitment/ training/ retraining/ mastering. Nowadays, health and its protection are not a simple relationship between a doctor and a patient. Healthcare is a dynamic-functional system of society.

The development and refinement of healthcare at every step is essential to the introduction of complex measures aimed at each individual, ultimately enabling the maintenance and continuous improvement of the health of

the whole community. In such an important and ongoing process, there is a list of problems that need to be addressed by consolidating specialists in many areas. One of the major problems in Georgia is the implementation of measures to improve the primary health care system. Despite many attempts and sufficient financial support from both international donors and the Georgian government, the reorganization is not being carried out at a sufficient pace, sometimes the problem itself is deep and difficult to eliminate. This can be evidenced by the negative assessments of the population as well as the medical staff employed in the primary health care facility and distrust towards the primary health care system. This is facilitated by the creation of numerous alternative services. We conducted an original study that focused on health care quality control research.

2. Materials and Methods

-Our research was like this. We examined patient responses to health services against the backdrop of technology standardization. The model provides for process optimization, including optimization of wage systems, and the search for additional sources of funding;

-development of the material technical base of the institution and supply management;

-continuous personnel training system; high social protection of employees, including through alternative sources of funding;

-managing resistance to innovation, including through adequate staff motivation;

-ensuring patient safety (risk management);

-continuous improvement of quality indicators.

Optimality criteria were taken as the basis for the quality improvement strategy.

3. Results

The basis for the fulfillment of the assigned tasks was the use of economic motivation of employees: remuneration for the final result of work. Monitoring, which includes elements of personalized accounting for the actual costs of medical services provided, allows a differentiated approach to the distribution of income among medical departments. Clinical and economic analysis of the activities of a particular doctor and nurse provides for the following types of management accounting: analysis of the volume of medical care and financial costs at each stage of medical care; elimination of processes that do not add

value; making managerial decisions to improve the system for the provision of polyclinic care; reducing the variability of the processes.

4. Discussion

We conducted an original study that focused on health care quality control research. There is no doubt about the advantages of setting up diagnostic centers, family medicine centers, and emergency centers. For example, financial contributions increase in the employment rate of doctors and so on. However, often such institutions fail to meet requirements such as access to the primary health care system, patient satisfaction (adequacy and high quality of medical care provided). Meanwhile, a so-called Vicious circle is developed. The state, foreign donors, and the medical community, despite many attempts, have failed to ensure a perfect management of material base and resources. One of the goals of the structural-organizational changes of the system may have been to reform the primary health care institution into family medicine centers. In this regard, with the help of foreign donors quite significant work was done in the 90s in Georgia. Nevertheless, serious shifts in the system still failed. Today, trained family doctors working in family medicine centers are well able to realize the acquired qualifications. The Municipal Social Insurance Program has long proven the superiority of family physicians over district therapists and pediatricians. Data from the World Health Organization confirm this. According to the pre-pandemic period, considering the purchasing power parity of the population of Georgia, the share of own funds spent by one patient is much higher compared to most countries in Europe and Asia. Currently, under pandemic conditions, this difference is maintained. A comprehensive analysis of the socio-economic effectiveness of primary health care will enable us to develop and expose scientifically sound recommendations based on the results obtained. In this regard, we consider it necessary to conduct research in the following areas: a) to identify the features of the main strategies for the development of the primary health care system in Georgia; b) Analysis of the main stages of reform of the primary health care sector, the impact of this process on the socio-economic situation of the society and the health care of the population; c) Determining the tendencies and qualitative similarities of the country's primary health care sector in approaching international standards; d) the importance of primary health care in the strategic development plan of the country (the urgency of this direction has increased even more in the conditions of COVID-19); e) To determine

the impact of socio-economic determinants on access to primary health care (the urgency of this direction has increased even more in the context of COVID- 19). Summarizing the results in the above direction and discussing the issue will ensure the development of an algorithm for refining and perfecting the modern primary health care circle.

5. Conclusions

The choice of quality indicators is undoubtedly a crucial step. We gave priority to the critical points of the treatment and diagnostic process. To assess the work of general medical practices, level indicators were used. Due to the introduction of the presented management model, positive dynamics have been achieved in the clinical, economic and social results of the multidisciplinary polyclinic. Total quality management programs have become a sine qua non condition for competing in today's markets. This is especially important in a pandemic caused by a new coronavirus.

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CARING FOR MEDICAL STAFF DURING A PANDEMIC COVID-19

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Abstract

Since April last ye, we have studied peculiarities of the epidemic process related to COVID-19 in Georgia. In the article was described risks of all medical workers during an epidemic, all medical workers, without exception, are subject to greater risk of infection compared to other categories of the population. We composed special questioners for doctors. We asked them standard questions: about dangerous of COVID-19 for them and needing psychological support. The tests used in this study is easy to process statistically. Our results showed that for 48% of the surveyed doctors believe that COVID-19 is dangerous for all people alone, 40% of 4 surveyed doctors believe that COVID-19 is dangerous for certain groups of the population, only 2% of the surveyed doctors consider it dangerous for personal health and 10 % of the surveyed doctors believe that the danger is exaggerated. Fifty percent of the surveyed doctors were willing to receive psychological support.

Keywords: COVID-19; health of doctors; psychological support.

1. Introduction

The main problem for World healthcare in 2020 is a pandemic of COVID-19. The coronavirus epidemic was first reported in December 2019 in Wuhan, Hubei Province, China. On March 11, 2020, the World Health Organization declared the coronavirus epidemic a global pandemic [1].

A person infected with COVID-19 was first identified in Georgia on February 26, 2020. After the first case was detected, the Minister of Health Ekaterine Tikaradze held a special briefing for the public. The coronavirus epidemic was first reported in December 2019 in Wuhan, Hubei Province, China. On March 11, 2020, the World Health Organization declared the coronavirus epidemic a global pandemic [2]. More than one and half years has passed since the announcement of the World Health Organization pandemics COVID-19.

Pandemic inflicted serious damage on the physical health of large groups of people, giving birth to a multitude of social and psychological problems. There are results of studies on the impact of pandemics or persistent measures (such as social distancing, self-isolation, the need to carry a mass) of different categories of population [3,4]. Since April 1, 2020, we have studied the laws, peculiarities of the epidemic process related to COVID-19 in Georgia. There are a lot of science literature which dedicated to therapeutic, diagnostic, measurements problem in groups patients with COVID-10, but only small part of the scientific literature dedicated to the psycho-somatic state of the doctors. Undoubtedly, the physical and mental health and emotional state of medical workers in conditions of increasing prevalence of infectious and viral diseases need special attention. Health and life of a huge number of people depend on doctor's self-control and the ability to deal with aggression. During an epidemic, all medical workers, without exception, are subject to greater risk of infection compared to other categories of the population. Doctors who directly deal with the patients with COVID-19 have greater danger [5]. This is staff of the emergency department, resuscitation departments. The increased risk of infection and disease, change in working conditions, high risk and liability, the need for permanent work in particular causes stress. This leads to increased anxiety, depressive state, emotional burnout, etc. In connection with the necessity of studying the impact of pandemic on doctor's health, there is a need study of risk factors and protective factors on mental health. When examining the psychological state of staff during a pandemic, attention is paid to different indicators, in the first instance, similar symptoms of depression and anxiety, the prevalence of which is shown. For study of our main goal,

we composed special questioners.

Doctors had to answer on some questions:

- COVID - 19 dangerous for the health of all people, for the health of certain groups of people, dangerous personally for the health of her/himself or the degree of danger COVID-19 for the health strongly exaggerated?
- Does doctor need a psychological support or not?

2. Materials and Methods

As the main research methodology, a test was used to measure the degree of a person's perception of life situations as stressful. The scale studies the emotional state of a person, studies the ability to understand the situation and the desire to receive psychological help. The questionnaire can be filled out quickly and easily. The test used in this study is easy to process statistically. Respondents were asked two sets of questions related to the COVID-19 pandemic. The block of closed points included the following: assessing the level of danger of COVID-19 to health, what causes them anxiety in connection with COVID-19 and whether they need psychological assistance in working conditions during a pandemic. Doctors-woman and doctors-man to each other were in a ratio of 5: 1. The average age of all subjects was 35 ± 3.4 years.

3. Results

Our results showed that for 48% of the surveyed doctors believe that COVID-19 is dangerous for all people alone, 40% of 4 surveyed doctors believe that COVID-19 is dangerous for certain groups of the population, only 2% of the surveyed doctors consider it dangerous for personal health and 10 % of the surveyed doctors believe that the danger is exaggerated. Fifty percent of the surveyed doctors were willing to receive psychological support.

4. Discussion

In terms of assessing the health risks of COVID-19, most of the study participants were divided into two equal groups according to their beliefs: those who believed that COVID-19 was dangerous to the health of the entire population and those who considered it dangerous only for health of certain groups. At the same time, almost a fifth expressed doubts about

the danger of the new coronavirus. A very small part of the respondents recognized the possible danger of COVID-19 for their own health. The percentage of study participants who wish to receive psychological help is equal to the percentage of study participants who do not wish to receive psychological help. Stress levels during a pandemic are higher for female doctors than for male colleagues. Revealed regular differences in the level of stress of medical workers, depending on the current situation (the number of infected and deaths) in the region of residence. The stress level is higher for those professionals who are forced to work in stressful conditions due to the difficult epidemiological situation. A connection was found between different beliefs in relation to COVID-19. Perhaps considering the relationship between beliefs and stress levels over time, it would be possible to draw conclusions about whether the perception of stress is actually mitigated by denial of danger. There is evidence that it is those who take the danger more seriously and experience higher stress at the initial stage, later on, are more prepared for the unfavorable development of the situation, which allows them to avoid adverse consequences. On the contrary, the fact that doctors, who do not take danger as seriously as their colleagues, have lower stress levels compared to others, in the early stages of a pandemic and other emergencies, can play an important role in terms of the optimal organization of professional activities and the distribution of functions between employees [6].

Unfortunately, the overwhelming majority of respondents, as in many similar studies, are women, which makes it difficult to assess the impact of the pandemic on the psychological state of male medical workers. The question of gender differences in the level of stress remains open when it comes to its dynamics in a changing environment. Another limitation is the inability to include in the study more variables that mitigate or exacerbate stress. Given the severe physical and mental stress on medical staff during the pandemic, when the study was conducted, we minimized the time spent by the respondents.

5. Conclusions

Such research is very important. Because the effective treatment of infected patients is associated with the health of the medical staff. One of the factors of health is the psychological state of a person. Correct organization of doctors' working hours and the attraction of a large number of male doctors to covid clinics will have a positive impact on management.

Acknowledgments

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AUTOMATION OF MAKING MARKETING DECISIONS

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Abstract

The article considers the application of complex marketing analysis to predict the sales volume of an organization, in order to plan the optimal amount of costs and assess the risks of making marketing decisions. The given method is not the usual prediction of the indicator by indicator, and takes into account the interaction of the studied indicator with various market factors. An information technology corresponding to the method was developed using the Ms Excel package.

Keywords: sales volume; factor of influence; trend; prediction; correlation; prediction error

1. Introduction

Market of goods and services represents complex system model with big amount of external and internal factors. Market situations has its own factors, but it's impossible to do future predictions of company sells based only tendency of concrete market factor. It is clear, many different factors can have influence on volume of sells as one of the most important market index: volume of competitors' sales, capacity of segment, conjuncture of goods or service and etc. Such influence decide behaviour not only volume of sales, also behaviour other market indicators. In accordance with this environment, it's necessary to be part of marketing research to do prediction of market tendency [1].

Let's discuss such task, organization needs to predict amount of sales of its own goods (service). We mean, market doesn't have any monopolists, there is no monopoly influence and behaviour on market situation - Many small and average enterprises are functioning on market. It's necessary to predict sales volume of enterprise for planning purchasing volume of enterprise and rate risk to make marketing decision.

2. Selection Influential factors on sales volume

Research began with selection of factors which cause changes into volume of sales, that's means creation of hypothesis about factors which can influence

on behaviour of sales curve. Choosing of factors happens with expert rule. Experts ask to name factors, which is part of marketing environment of organization, with external and internal factors and have influence on sales. It means, math dynamic of this factors are known on the same intervals, where we have volume of sales. Some external factors are exchange rate, volume of the consumer segment, volume of total sum of this segment, dynamic of number change of competitors' and etc. Some internal factors are supplies of goods, effective management of organization, type of advertisement and its costs, positioning of goods, number of distributors and etc. Chose factors are unlimited. In general high rate of factors represents accurate prediction results. With expert analysis chose three abstract factor: F_1 , F_2 , F_3 . See example down below (table. 1).

Table 1
F1-F3 factors, which has influence on Q Volume of sales

Month	<i>Volume of Sales</i> Q	<i>Factors</i>		
		F_1	F_2	F_3
March	23	22	12	240
April	34	36	2	280
May	55	45	3	318
June	35	58	67	260
July	24	77	32	325
August	37	99	22	254
September	43	102	33	312
October	45	111	89	285
November	56	122	11	324

Sift out of influence factors. This stage involves identifying factors, which have a significant impact on changes in sales volume, the remaining factors will be removed from the discussion. The correlation coefficient can be considered as a criterion for such acceleration, which show how close the

tendency is each of the two factors in time. F_1 , F_2 , F_3 factors probabilistic distributions Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Dynamics of research factors

Table. 2 represent Q volume of sales and the values of the coefficients of correlation between F_1 , F_2 , F_3 factors, Excel has CORREL function. Calculation shows, that F_1 and F_3 are essential factors according Correlation coefficients, and it's possible to remove F_2 factor from discussion, this last one has no influence

Table 2

Q	F_1	F_2	F_3
23	22	12	240
34	36	2	280
55	45	3	318
35	58	67	260
24	77	32	325
37	99	22	254
43	102	33	312
45	111	89	285
56	122	11	324
	K(Q,F1)	K(Q,F2)	K(Q,F3)
σ	0.492	-0.044	0.520

Predicting Impact Factors. In our case, we have dynamics of influencing factors and sales volume during the March-November period and we try to predict the behavior of each factor over the next four months. With the dynamics of the factors, we use a linear functional model for prediction, which is implemented through the FORECAST function of the Excel package (table. 3) [2,3].

Table 3

<i>F1</i>	<i>F3</i>
22	240
36	280
45	318
58	260
77	325
99	254
102	312
111	285
122	324
140	316
152	314
165	316
177	328

Sales forecasting according to the forecast of impact factors. It is impossible to predict sales only according to the sales trend over time, whereas, it will be the prediction of the research factor itself according to this factor. But we also have a trend of influencers, which in its essence, as it appears from the calculated correlation coefficients, determines the behavior of the sales curve. It is this predicted trend that allows us to forecast sales volume according to the values of the factors. This value (Q TREND) is calculated as the arithmetic mean of the predicted values (Q1 TREND, Q3 TREND) according to individual factors (Table 4).

Estimation of forecasting errors. We must keep in mind that forecasting takes place under certain assumptions, which affects the quality of the forecast. These are assumptions:

- The factor that does not have a significant impact on the study rate may not be included in the analysis;

-The above methodology uses linear forecasting, while the functional relationship between market indicators may be more complex.

-The predictive value of the study indicator is calculated as the arithmetic mean of the predicted values according to the factors, without taking into account the level of correlation of the relevant factor.

Table 4

<i>Q</i>	<i>Q TREND</i>	<i>F1</i>	<i>Q1 TREND</i>	<i>F3</i>	<i>Q3 TREND</i>
23		22		240	
34		36		280	
55		45		318	
35		58		260	
24		77		325	
37		99		254	
43		102		312	
45		111		285	
56		122		324	
	47.0	140	49.7	316	44.3
	45.9	152	48.2	314	43.5
	46.0	165	47.7	316	44.2
	55.9	177	69.8	328	42.0

These assumptions certainly reduce the accuracy of the prediction. Moreover, the periods that follow in December of the current year are forecasted not on the basis of time-tested values, but also on the basis of mathematically predicted data. This means that the longer the period of time we try to predict, the less accurate the predicted values can be.

The above limitations indicate the need to calculate forecasting error (risk). In the case of our methodology, this error can be estimated according to the projected values of sales trend (*Q TREND*) and the projected values of sales for each factor (*Q1 TREND* and *Q3 TREND*). In particular, the calculation of the error is based on the calculation of the average value ratio of the average deviations of the forecast values and the sales trend:

$$\text{VAR} = ((\text{ABS}(\text{QTREND} - \text{Q1TREND}) + \text{ABS}(\text{QTREND} - \text{Q3TREND})) / 2) / \text{QTREND}.$$

The results of the calculation of the forecast error (VAR) using the MS Excel package are as follows table. 5.

Forecasting errors are taken into account by adjusting the percentage of sales according to its percentage value. In our case, taking into account the 6% forecast error, it is advisable to plan the next volume of sales for December this year:

$$Q = \text{QTREND} \times \text{VAR} = 47.0 \times 0.94 = 44.18$$

Table 5.
About Q.

<i>Q TREND</i>	<i>F1</i>	<i>Q1 TREND</i>	<i>F3</i>	<i>Q3 TREND</i>	<i>VAR</i>	<i>VAR %</i>
47.0	140	49.7	316	44.3	0.057	6%
45.9	152	48.2	314	43.5	0.051	5%
46.0	165	47.7	316	44.2	0.038	4%
55.9	177	69.8	328	42.0	0.249	25%

3. Conclusion

Factors influencing sales volume were identified based on expert opinions to substantiate the marketing decision of sales volume planning. Subsequently, based on the analysis of correlation coefficients, the factors whose influence on the study index were insignificant were excluded. The values of the influencing factors were predicted and sales volume was forecasted based on them. The forecasting error was estimated and the forecasted sales volume was adjusted according to it.

The discussed methodology can be used for any number of influencing factors. Due to the dynamics of the factors and in order to reduce the prediction errors, other functional prediction models can be used instead of the linear model.

Acknowledgments

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MENTAL ILLNESS AND VIOLENCE - ACCESS TO MENTAL HEALTH SERVICES AND MULTIDISCIPLINARY APPROACH PRIORITIES

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Abstract

The relationship between mental disorder and violence still remains extremely important for both professionals and the general public. Is it possible to reduce the risk of violent behavior? The study of these issues is crucial both in terms of public health and for the proper planning and development of mental health services. A national reform of mental healthcare in Georgia has been undergoing for the past fifteen years with the aim of moving to a balanced care model, developing community services and promoting reintegration of people with mental disorders into the community. This, in turn, requires a better understanding of the risk factors of violent behavior to address complex needs of these people. The aim of this survey was to explore relationship between clinical needs, treatment engagement and violence in patients with schizophrenia and schizophrenia spectrum disorders (SSD) using case control design. Cases were defined as patients with SSD who have committed at least one act of violence in the past. Controls were gender- and age matched patients with SSD who have never committed such acts of violence. 94 patients were assessed in case group and 106 patients in control group. We studied the impact of various potential risk factors on each person through patient interviews and medical records. Study results showed that the data were quite variable depending on the type of treatment setting. According

to survey results, the dynamic interaction of social and contextual factors with treatment engagement played an important role as determinants of violence. Study results demonstrated that access to mental health community services and multidisciplinary team approach was associated with a better outcome for individuals with SSD. Therefore, studies of violence among individuals with mental disorders should go beyond linking various conditions or types with severity or frequency of violence, and instead focus on in-depth research on contextual and comorbid factors to identify the complex patterns of interaction. Only with such an approach is it possible to plan appropriate interventions and provide to patients in community settings. Finally, reliable data are needed to properly inform the public about the relation between mental illness and violence, to avoid potentially unwarranted stigmatization associated with mental illness.

Keywords: mental illness; violence; schizophrenia; risk factors

1. Introduction

There is a widespread public perception that people with mental disorders are dangerous and liable to violent crimes. This society perception contributes to the stigma faced by people with mental disorders, which in turn contributes to non-disclosure of the mental illness and decreased treatment seeking [1]. Recent meta-analyses have shown that there is a modest association between Schizophrenia Spectrum Disorders (SSDs) and increased risk of violent crime [2]. In an epidemiological study, Swanson and colleagues found that the 1-year prevalence of violent behavior in schizophrenia was 8.4%, compared with only 2.1% in those without mental illness [3]. The study which analyzed violent behavior among persons with schizophrenia committed crime in forensic settings showed that 40% of the offenders with schizophrenia had concurrent substance abuse, higher than a comparison group of individuals with schizophrenia in the community, of whom 26% abused substances [4]. Recent review of factors associated with severe violence in schizophrenia revealed that substance abuse was robustly linking schizophrenia and violence [5].

Most researchers and professionals agree that a combination of various biological and psycho-social factors play a role in violence and aggression, although there are differing opinions regarding the importance of individual factors [6]. However, general conclusions including the following: severe mental disorder alone is not a sufficient predictor of future violence; important role plays such factors as historical (past violence, physical abuse, juvenile detention, parental arrest), clinical (substance use, perceived threats,

treatment adherence), dispositional (age, sex, income) and contextual (recent unemployment, divorce, victimization). In conclusion, the author points out that people with severe mental disorders are still more likely to engage in violent acts, largely because of other contributory factors associated with violence [7]. A national reform of mental healthcare in Georgia has been undergoing for the past fifteen years with the aim of moving to a balanced care model, developing community services and promoting reintegration of people with mental disorders into the community. To achieve this goal Georgia should undertake appropriate steps to shift from institutional care towards community based mental health services. This, in turn, requires a better understanding of the risk factors of violent behavior of people with mental disorders to address complex needs of these people. Is violent behavior common in people with schizophrenia? Which clinical and additional risk factors influence aggressive behavior? The study of these issues is crucial both in terms of public health and for the proper planning and development of mental health services. The aim of this survey was to explore relationship between clinical needs, treatment engagement and violence in patients with schizophrenia and schizophrenia spectrum disorders (SSD) using case-control design. In our survey, we hypothesized that cases compare to controls have experienced greater exposure to a range of violence risk factors that include: more severe positive symptoms, concurrent substance misuse, lack of family or social support and poor treatment engagement.

2. Materials and Methods

The study design was case-control study linked to retrospective study of medical records. Case-control groups were defined according to the outcome. Cases were defined as patients with SSD who have committed at least one act of violence in the past and at the time of survey were treated in the mental health forensic department at the National Mental Health Centre (Khoni, Georgia) Controls were gender-and age matched patients with SSD who have never committed an act of violence in the past and were recruited from in-patient and outpatient mental health settings located in Khoni and Rustavi (Georgia). Formal inclusion criteria for participants were men and women of age 18–65 who met diagnostic criteria for schizophrenia and schizophrenia spectrum disorders based on the International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems 10th Revision (ICD-10) [8]. Written informed consent was obtained from the all study participants. Patients were excluded if they had a diagnosis of mental retardation, or other cognitive disorder, presented persistent severe psychotic symptoms, demonstrated lack

of adequate decision-making capacity to make a choice about participating in the research. A total of 200 patients were recruited for the study; 94 patients in the violent-case group and 106 patients in the nonviolent-control group. Data were collected through patient interviews and medical records. We explored the impact of various potential risk factors on each person (socio-demographic, substance misuse, psychotic and negative symptoms, non-compliance with treatment, use of mental health services, impulsivity and global level of functioning) using a retrospective method. All study participants were assessed with a standard set of instruments over 2 weeks in Dec 2019 and Jan 2020. Demographic information on education, living conditions, marriage status, past medical and treatment history was obtained from patients' medical records. Scale for the assessment of positive and negative symptoms (SANS, SAPS) [9] was used to rate the severity of participants' illness. Positive and negative symptoms scale is a rating 5-point scale from 0 (absent) to 5 (severe) to measure positive (hallucination, delusion, disorganized thoughts, bizarre behavior) and negative (attention deficit, anhedonia, alogia, avolition, blunted affect) symptoms in Schizophrenia. The Global Assessment of Functioning (GAF) [10] Scale was used to rate how much a person's mental illness affect their day-to-day life. GAF considers psychological, social, and occupational functioning on a hypothetical continuum of mental health-illness from 1-10 inability to function to 90-100 highest level of functioning. Do not include impairment in functioning due to physical (or environmental) limitations. Data were analyzed using IBM SPSS statistics version 23. Study group was defined as a dichotomous variable with the categories 'cases' and 'controls'. Exposure to risk factors was measured by Odds Ratio (OR) at 95% confidence intervals (CI). Quantitative parameters were compared between groups by the independent sample t-test. The comparison of qualitative parameters between the groups was performed by chi-square test. For further analysis of their association a multivariable logistic regression model was used. $P < 0.05$ was considered significant.

3. Results

Sample characteristics Data were available for 200 participants. In case group 90.4% of the respondents were male (mean age 39.8 years), in controls 86.8% -were male (mean age 41.3 years). Only 19.1% of cases and 16.0% of controls were married. 24.5% in case group had incomplete secondary school education versus 7.5 in control group. Only 8.5% of cases had completed high education versus 17% in controls. Clinical aspects Hallucinations if presented were less severe compared with controls (7.5% vs 2.1 in cases). Persecutory

delusion was significantly higher in case group Negative symptoms were marked in cases but more severe in controls. Of cases 34% showed moderate impairment of global functioning (vs 22,6% of controls) and 43,6% serious impairment (vs 25,5%) (Table 1).

History of illness and use of mental health services There was no significant difference between groups in the duration of identified mental health problems. 34% of the case sample had used some mental health services and 44.7% used irregularly (77.4% and 22.6% respectively in controls).

Table 1

Assessment of psychotic and negative symptoms (SAPS, SANS),
(P Value <0.05)

Clinical symptoms	Cases (at the time of offence)	Controls (at the time of survey)	P-value
Global rating of hallucinations			.000
None	24,5%	6,6%	
Moderate	40,4%	35,8%	
Marked	29,8%	26,4%	
Severe	2,1%	7,5%	
Rating of aggressive/agitated behaviour			.000
None	4,3%	32,1%	
Moderate	41,5%	20,8%	
Marked	40,4%	13,2%	
Severe	2,1%	0,1%	
Global rating of affective flattening			.000
None	3,2%	3,8%	
Moderate	54,3%	39,6%	
Marked	34,0%	17,9%	
Severe	0,0%	0,0%	
Global rating of avolition/apathy			.000

None	2,1%	0,9%	
Moderate	33,0%	48,1%	
Marked	58,5%	26,4%	
Severe	1,1%	1,9%	
Global rating of anhedonia/ asociality			.001
None	1,1%	1,9%	
Moderate	44,7%	27,4%	
Marked	44,7%	35,8%	
Severe	2,1%	7,5%	
Global assessment of functioning			.000
Mild impairment	2,1%	18,9%	
Moderate impairment	34,0%	22,6%	
Serious impairment	43,6%	25,5%	
Severe impairment	20,2%	33,0%	

Most frequently used services were psychiatry hospitals (35.1% of cases and 25.5% of controls). Only 4.3% of cases were compliant with treatment (vs 51.9% of controls) (Table 2).

Table 2
Factors associated with identification of mental illness and treatment adherence (P Value<0.05).

Characheristic	Cases	Controls
Use of mental health services (last year)		
Yes	34,0%	77,4%
No	21,3%	0,0%
Irregularly	44,7%	22,6%
What MH services were used		
Psychiatry hospital	35,1%	25,5%
Narcology hospital	5,3%	0,0%

MH outpatient clinic	26,6%	45,3%
MH mobile team	0,0%	29,2%
Private visits	6,4%	0,0%
Prison MH services	6,4%	0,0%
Compliance to treatment		
Yes	4,3%	51,9%
No	28,7%	13,2%
Reason for non-compliance		
I don't need	24,5%	17,9%
It makes me feel bad	19,1%	23,6%
I don't want to be controlled	12,8%	,9%
I am forgetting	6,4%	0,0%

Based on multivariable regression modeling, violent behaviour was significantly more likely to have experienced contextual risk factors, such as: (Table 3)

- [a] Unsatisfied living environment
- [b] Low level of education
- [c] Unemployment
- [d] Lack of contacts with mental health services
- [e] Non-compliance to treatment
- [f] Drug abuse
- [g] Lack of social contact or communication skills
- [h] Family conflicts

4. Discussion

Bivariate analyses showed that the incidence of violent behavior was higher for people with more severe psychotic symptoms, concurrent substance misuse, lack of access to mental health services and poor treatment adherence. Our analysis also showed that high negative psychotic symptoms were significantly associated with reduced risk of serious violence. Study results suggested, that non-adherence with medication, especially in conjunction with substance misuse problems, was associated with increased risk of reoffending. Several studies have documented the link between

alcohol consumption and the occurrence of aggressive behavior. However, the results of this study showed that there was no significant difference between the control group and the cases of alcohol abuse. Study of this issue is recommended for further research.

Table 3
Factors associated with violent behaviour cases versus psychiatric controls

Factors	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)
Step Alcohol abuse	1,452	,966	2,258	1	,133	4,270
1 ^a Married status	-2,425	,968	6,272	1	,012	,088
Unsatisfied living enviroment	4,677	1,033	20,487	1	,000	107,420
Low level of education	2,606	1,078	5,843	1	,016	13,547
High education level	2,085	1,208	2,979	1	,084	8,046
Unemployment (last year)	-2,679	1,036	6,684	1	,010	,069
Salary/Income	2,868	1,259	5,190	1	,023	17,608
Social aid	1,665	,818	4,145	1	,042	5,287
Use of mental health services (last year)	2,452	,783	9,812	1	,002	11,617
Irregular use of mental health services (last year)	-20,001	7093,247	,000	1	,998	,000
Compliance to treatment	1,182	,616	3,678	1	,055	3,261
Drug abuse	-2,154	,759	8,056	1	,005	,116
Lack of socialization (personal/distance contacts)	2,019	,960	4,420	1	,036	7,528
Family conflicts	-1,896	,675	7,882	1	,005	,150
Lack of communication skills	-1,599	,755	4,486	1	,034	,202
Constant	-5,216	1,647	10,026	1	,002	,005

a. Variable(s) entered on step 1 alcohol abuse _ family status _ married, loving environment _ satisfactory, medium _ high level of education, employment, income_code_1, social aid_code_2, mh services_1, _mh services_2, treatment adherence, drug abuse, socialization_3_4, conflicts_family conflictsi_1, communication_ability_none.

This study has limitations, sometimes including reliance on expert opinions rather than verifiable facts about possible events related to violence, including the assessment of psychiatric symptoms. There are additional limitations in the current study. Self-reported violence as used in surveys likely underestimates actual violence in controls and the time span may have affected recall of important life events. The third limitation is that participants of the control group may not be representative of all persons with schizophrenia, as they represent a group of treated patients who were willing to enroll in a survey. So the study excluded treatment-rejected patients (who might have been more violent) and, thus, the findings cannot generalize to such patients.

According to survey results, the dynamic interaction of social and contextual factors with clinical variables played an important role as determinants of violence. Study results demonstrated that the adequate treatment with interdisciplinary approach, including the management of comorbid substance abuse was associated with a better outcome for individuals with severe mental disorders. Promoting medication adherence and abstinence together during periods of prolonged leave from hospital or initial discharge may therefore significantly reduce risk of re-offending.

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SENSORY DISCRIMINATION IN NEURAL NETWORKS OF DISSOCIATED CORTICAL CULTURE

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Abstract

For the acquisition and discrimination of sensory information, the nervous system comprises a variety of structural and functional instruments. These processes occur in accordance with the brain's physical nature and involve many of its labyrinths. On the other hand, the brain's complexity may pose a challenge in determining the correct mechanisms. Answering the question of why cerebral circuitry prefers some sensory stimuli over others could help us understand how we identify diversity in the world. Modeling the neuronal network in the dissociated cortical culture (DCC) homed on a multielectrode array (MEA) may help to tackle the problem and give

an easier setting for research. This *in vivo-like in vitro* system of around 100000 neuronal and glial cells eventually build simplified but realistic neural structure and persist to exist for about two months on MEA. That allows to follow and measure structural and functional refinement and the potential for calculations and coding of information in the newly developed neural circuits as well as to understand the role of activity at the single neuron level that determines effective behavior. Following a month of *in vitro* development of DCC, pairs of electrodes were employed to simulate a variety of sensory inputs using various types of electric stimulation. Single, paired-pulse ((PP; 20 ms interstimulus interval) and 1, 5, 10, 20, and 50 Hz 300 mV stimuli of 1 s duration were repeated after every 20 s or at a random time interval. All channels that exhibited appropriate level of activity were monitored. Experiments revealed that registered channels tended to respond solely to one of the stimulus paradigms, creating or enhancing activity while suppressing responses to other stimuli. The most effective stimulus paradigm was PP stimuli in most cases, however specific cases indicated the efficiency of other stimulus paradigms as well. Even higher frequency stimuli had a chance to be beneficial in situations where low frequency stimuli were generally more effective. Both tonic and burst features were present in multicellular and single-unit responses. Many cases pointed to a phenomenon that academics rarely pay attention to: replies that took more than 300 ms. They drew our attention since they showed selectivity to stimulator patterns as well. We revealed instant and delayed evoked responses that were not present before certain stimuli were administered, which may be regarded as gradual steps of sensory information processing by neural networks. Simultaneously, frequent exposure to the favored stimuli increased the occurrence of immediate reactions that demonstrated synaptic plasticity for memory formation. Data shows that DCC's small neural networks are highly sensitive to physical characteristics of sensory input, allowing sensory discrimination.

Keywords: dissociated cortical culture; multielectrode array; sensory discrimination; *in vivo-like in vitro*; neural network

1. Introduction

Human ambitions to decode the brain's intricate nature and develop similar artificial and cyborg systems are growing rapidly in our century. Brain-machine systems, in particular, are of particular interest because they have limitless potential in the medical area and in human life [1].

A modern effective scientific approach for registration of multiple

electrophysiological signals, modeling brain to body feedback system, and even development of prototypes of neuroprosthetic devices is an *in vivo like in vitro* system of dissociated cortical culture (DCC) grown on the multielectrode array (MEA). During development, bare neural cells from dissociated cortical tissue change shape and acquire axons and dendrites that connect to one another, forming neural networks that are comparable to those found in neural tissue. Action potentials are generated by neurons. Implanted on the glass surface electrodes designed for both stimulation and recording in the parallel regime allow to imitate sensory inputs over various areas of neural culture on the one hand, and to record a variety of evoked electric neural signals from the entire surface on the other hand, which reflect the complex nature of information processing [2].

They can be utilized as inputs to sophisticated algorithms that control body parts, robotic prosthesis, and virtual animations. It was possible in several works to develop feedback cyborg systems of DCC and robotic body, in which neural network received information about robotic body in permanent manner, could save information and could improve performance by experience, that actually depended on the neural plasticity processes in the neuronal culture. Similar cyborg systems enable to learn how to employ brain signals for managing machines, at one hand and to examine high nervous functions in the highly suitable long-term opened visible dynamic preparation of the forming neural networks, on the other hand [3].

Approaches of prior cyborg systems of the DCC and robotic body (or virtual body) depended on the evoked responses of selected stimuli that were utilized for coding information and decoding patterns of spike responses for driving cybernetic parts [4]. We came up with the idea of using this technology to imitate various types of sensory information and investigate the fundamentals of sensory discrimination processes in such a small colony of roughly 100000 neural cells that eventually grow and construct neural networks and resemble neural tissue. We wanted to know if it's conceivable in small neural networks, and if so, how and when it happens. What kind of kinetics may it have?

We mastered the production of long-living DCCs for these purposes, which were allowed to mature for one month in MEA. At one month of *in vitro* cultivation, DCC was subjected to a variety of electric stimuli, employing the same and/or distinct inputs (pair of electrodes) to simulate varied sensory patterns. During stimulations, continuous registration of neuronal responses was carried out, revealing varied patterns of early and late responses across the culture area.

Data show that neuronal networks of DCC contain great selectivity to

physical attributes and spatial position of sensory input, allowing for sensory discrimination. Instant and delayed evoked responses should reflect instant and delayed information processing, with the likelihood of rapid responses increasing during training sessions with preferred stimuli, indicating engaged memory formation neural plasticity mechanisms. Simultaneously, it highlights some of the complexity of sensory discrimination by emphasizing the gradual nature of information processing.

2. Materials and Methods

Experiments were carried out according to the norms of the international animal care and use committee (IACUC) and bioethics committee of Free University of Tbilisi.

Preparation of DCC. DCCs were prepared according to the standard approaches with significant modifications to meet our experimental demands. The major manual belongs to the competent group of Potter [5] that define techniques concerning the preparation, care and electrophysiological registration from the DCC on the multielectrode array. At the 18th day of pregnancy, cortical pieces were taken from the brain of a rat fetus (total number 36 from the 12 litters). The use of a biosafety cabinet class 2 and 70% alcohol helped to ensure sterility. To insert cortical pieces and clear neural tissue from blood and arachnoid tissue, a cold Hanks balanced salt solution was utilized. In order to inhibit excitatory processes linked to seizures, excitotoxicity and apoptosis in a mechanically dissociated brain tissue Kynurenic acid (final concentration 1 mM) and selective agonist of NMDA receptors, AP5 (0.025 mM final concentration) were added to solution. For tissue fermentive digestion, a mixture of active papain (15 units) and DNase (50 μ M) was utilized for 20 minutes. Digested tissue remains were rinsed 3 times with culture medium that was CO₂ independent hibernation medium (from Thermofisher) with B27 plus supplement (2%) and fetal bovine serum (10%). Special microfilters with 40 μ m pores were employed to filter tissue remains in order to get clear colony of dissociated cells (neurons and glial cells together) and to clean solution from the remains of arachnoid tissue. After, bovine serum albumin was added to solution. It was centrifuged at 200x speed and rinsed out again with a final medium in order to remove toxins released during a process of tissue digestion and dissociation from the cells. Using a cytometer grid and a microscope, the concentration of cells was measured to be around 1000-2000 cells per μ l. Dilution or centrifugation were used to adjust for outreging of a standard concentration. We didn't try to separate neurons from glial cells because glial cells aid in

the survival of neurons and provide natural space for development. 10 μ l of cell suspension was poured over the surface of MEA central region, which itself was previously coated with polyethylenimine (0.05 %) and laminin (0.001 %) for 30 s. The cells were allowed to attach to the surface for 30 s before the final media was introduced to the culture. HEPES (hydroxyethyl-hyperazin-ethan-solphonic acid) solution (0.01 M final concentration) was used to ensure extra buffer characteristics of the surrounding tissue media. In the incubator, the temperature was 36°C and the humidity was 65 %. To ensure tissue with proper intrinsic cell survival factors, half of the medium was changed twice a week and the other half was left. To maintain sterile and hermetic conditions, a suitable glass cover was adapted to the ring of MEA. Neural culture was kept in those settings for around 2 months, that for our situation was an excellent duration during that tissue appeared healthy and it could generate action potentials. Morphological control. Under the microscope, morphological control of DCCs was done once during cytometric adjustment of cell concentration and twice weekly during the experiment. For it, an inversive digital microscope with magnification of 100X to 200X was used. Pictures were taken with the AMCAP program that came with the digital camera. Concentration of cells, cleanness of around area, cell position related to electrodes and development degree of the neural network was noticed during the microscopy. Pictures were collected from the same two areas in order to have better comparison conditions: One was the square area of 9 electrodes from electrode N22; the other was the square area of 9 electrodes from electrode N77. Differentiation quality of observed neural networks were evaluated by the length of neural fibers that was simply estimated by geometric approaches compared to the diameter of electrodes (30 μ m). Recording. Multichannel systems Co. is responsible for the setup of 60 channel systems for electrophysiological research (Germany). The main device, the MEA1060-UP-BC, is a preamplifier suited for 60 electrode MEA recordings and is capable of ensuring blanking circuitry allowing registration from the stimulating electrodes with the others; the preamplifier, stimulator STG4002, and the computer (with the supplied proper cardboard) are synchronized with each other to ensure coordinated work of the system; for registration, stimulation, and selection of the sets of stimulating, recording, and grounding electrodes and the Company's free softwares: MC_Rack, MC_Stimulus, and MEA_Select were utilized.

From a methodological standpoint, the stimulation techniques were perhaps the most crucial aspect of the experiment because different types of stimuli were connected with a diversity of sensory information. For single, paired-pulse stimulations with a 20 ms interstimulus interval and varying frequencies

of stimulations of 1, 5, 10, 20, 50, and 100 Hz of stimuli of 1 s duration, rectangular impulses with two phases of 100 μ s duration and tension of 300 mV were utilized. All types of stimulations were applied once every 20 s (or at a close random time interval) from a pair of electrodes, with the duration of the stimulation session changing according to the experimental protocols and recorded responses.

To begin registration sessions, the phases of spontaneous multi-neuronal activity, which served as a background level for evoked activity, were always used. The signals were amplified 10000 times and filtered with a high-pass filter (>200, with the function of Butterworth 2nd order). After that, stimulation operations were carried out, and registration was carried out for an appropriate amount of time. The multichannel layout of the registering software, as well as the used system, allowed for dimensional dispersion of the signal processing.

Analyses. The Python programming language was utilized to develop a data analysis program application pack (NeuroSpace) that was used to move data from MC_Rack files (mcd format) to appropriate graphical and numerical datafiles, which were then processed in the SPSS statistical program. NeuroSpace enabled the presentation of real-time signals from a specific channel, the separation of appropriate frequencies, the processing of specified partitions, the separation of single levels of neurons, the detection of neuronal vs network bursts, and the generation of appropriate datafiles. In total, 40 MC_Rack electrophysiological recordings were examined using this method. From cultures ranging in age from 25 to 35 days *in vitro* (DIV), electrophysiological data was compiled for this work. On the other hand, data were categorized according to the stimuli used: 300 mV single, paired-pulse with a 20 ms interstimulus interval and varying stimulation frequencies of 1, 5, 10, 20, 50, and 100 Hz for 1 s stimuli. The characteristics of interest for evaluation were the spike frequencies of multi-units and single-units, which were estimated before and after the applied stimulus paradigms. These comparisons were carried out in three different ways: 1. In short-term (up to 300 ms) periods; 2. In longer-term (up to 1000 ms) periods; and 3. In general activity levels generated by specific stimuli.

One-way ANOVA analyses were used to compare activity levels before and after stimuli (for both multiunit and single unit data). If early and later post-stimulus response areas were evaluated, Multifactorial ANOVA analyses were applied; and Multifactorial ANOVA analyses were utilized as well when pre- and post-stimulus activity levels were compared with different stimuli types.

3. Results

Morphology. Morphological monitoring of neuronal culture began on 0 DIV, when the cells had reached a sufficient concentration. At the time, cells represented oval/round shaped white entities with no fiber descendants. That also reveals that through enzymatic digestion neural tissue lost all properties adhering cell together that form neural tissue and we acquired dissociated healthy cells (Pic. 1, A). In the next time, morphological control was performed twice a week. Differentiated cell bodies were already observed at 3 DIV and axo-dendritic fibers reached about $40\pm 15\ \mu\text{m}$ after 7 DIV ($n=30$). Gradual increase of cell fibers were noticed in following weeks of cultivation: 60 ± 17 at 14 DIV, 80 ± 28 at 21 DIV that did not change significantly later (Pic. 1, B). After 3-4 weeks, not all cells showed fiber extension, but some did, as well as a consistent decrease in cell number over the counted region.

Electrophysiology. - Electrophysiological recordings of multiunit activity were done using the MC Rack program supplied by multichannel systems Co., and single-unit responses were isolated during analysis using the NeuroSpace software, which was built by us in Python. For this experiment, electrophysiological registration of DCC preparations was done exclusively from the 25 to 35 DIV samples in order to eliminate variable level in electrophysiological characteristics.

Fig.1. **A** - DCC on the hemocytometer, exhibiting adequate dispersion in the suspension and healthy cells. **B** - DCC at the day 25DIV, showing developed neuronal cells with axonal and dendritic fibers. **C** - Discrimination of multi-unit neuronal evoked responses to a variety of electric stimuli. Above the recordings applied paradigms are indicated. Black arrows show location of evoked responses generated in a short duration (≤ 300 ms) of applied stimulation. There is a change of quantity of activity in response to low frequency stimuli and particularly PP stimuli.

Neuronal signals of the spontaneous responses were registered initially and permitted for recording for around 10 minutes to develop a background level of activity before stimulation sessions were commenced. DCC preparations were characterized by substantial variation in development that led some channels to be more active compared to others, from which some channels never got activated. At the same time, spontaneous activity was characterized by a wide range of responses, from infrequent spikes to strong bursts that became more prominent with age. The essential condition for registration, however, was that the channel must have been active for long enough to have registered for both spontaneous and stimulation sessions (at least 30 min). After a spontaneous activity registration session, the pair of electrodes were used to elicit a range of electric stimulus sessions using random time intervals. Stimulation sessions revealed that a variety of electric stimuli elicited particular tonic and burst responses in DCC and that these responses were very variable. In most cases they displayed preferred responsiveness to low frequency and specifically, to 300 mV paired-pulse stimuli, when other forms of electric stimuli were neglected or decreased level of activity (Fig. 1, C). However, in unusual conditions, greater susceptibility to other types of stimuli was also observed (Fig. 1, C 4, 5, 6). At the same time, it was detected that when an electric stimulus coincided with enhanced network activity, especially bursts, inhibition was typically followed (Fig. 1, C 1). Changes in stimulation frequency or the relocation of stimulatory electrodes were other factors that caused alterations in the spatial distribution of electric responses. This frequently resulted in the activation of additional channels and/or a decrease of reactions in active channels. Furthermore, it was found that stimulation tension had a significant effect. When greater or weaker stimuli were largely neglected or had an inhibitory impact, an intermediate tension of about 300 mV was optimum for producing electric responses. At the same time, discrimination properties were so particular that even doubled version of PP stimuli were far from the effect that was shown with the PP stimuli.

In most cases, a rise in activity did not occur immediately, and some training sessions were required before the network was engaged. Unexpectedly, network activation started before occurrence of evoked responses, which only became prevalent after training sessions (Fig. 1, C 2). Typically, such registrations showed gradual activation of neural circuits that reached an optimal level before being inhibited again by the network. These stages were usually performed several times. Evoked responses largely related to PP stimuli. However, training sessions were necessary in order to increase the likelihood of its success (Fig. 1, C 2). Accordingly, data analyses required

a method for distributing specific examples and distinguishing between a background, training, and trained phases. As a result, trained networks still showed different probability of the evoked responses that reached approximately 60 % of cases for PP stimuli, 35-40 % for single or 5 Hz stimuli, about 15-20 % for 10 Hz stimuli, up to 10 % for 20 Hz and as low as 5 % for 50 and 100 Hz stimuli.

Delayed responses to certain stimuli with a latency of more than 300 ms were also the subject of interest. The data showed that they were largely tied to the specified favored stimuli and had little to do with other stimuli or random cases of spontaneous activity.

Data analyze at the neuronal level with NeuroSpace revealed that some of DCC single neurons in multiunit recordings reacted differently than the network as a whole, generating varying levels of responses on different types of stimuli (Pic. 1 C). The antagonistic nature of neuron populations was frequently highlighted by the spatial position of active channels, which promoted activity in some channels while inhibiting activity in others.

4. Discussion

MEA and related multichannel system setup make it possible to interface with DCC's neural networks in a near to the natural way, to stimulate any collection of electrodes, to record responses from the entire surface, and to analyze according long-term morpho-functional adjustments. This presents a perfect setting for studying sensory perception processes at the neural network level. In order to investigate the basics of sensory discrimination, we used a variety of electric stimuli from the same and different sources to imitate a variety of sensory inputs, recorded responses, and analyzed the potential of these reactions for coding and decoding a variety of information. Experiments revealed that DCC's newly built neural networks showed indications of basic level of sensory discrimination: active DCC regions responded to one of the supplied stimuli, establishing or raising levels of activity, while ignoring or lowering reactions to other stimuli. We found immediate and delayed evoked responses that were not present prior to the introduction of particular stimuli, indicating various steps of information processing. Simultaneously, training with the preferred stimuli resulted induced more frequent immediate responses, demonstrating triggered neuronal plasticity in the relevant neural circuits.

Previous research has shown that DCCs are responsive to some produced low frequency stimuli and inhibited by high frequency stimuli in independent investigations [6,7,8]. We gained ideas for simulation of numerous sensory

inputs from those studies, which may be accomplished by varying the frequency, intensity, or sequence of impulses.

Our study's main finding was that individual cultures, or even particular portions within the same culture, show great selectivity for one of the many stimuli and increase activity to that stimulation while activating less effectively or decreasing activity to other stimuli. In spite of the preference to the PP stimulus or single stimuli or low frequency stimuli, the physical structure and features of the particular network establish individual nature for selection. Surely, particular selectivity to electric stimuli can hint about the individual properties of the supplied neural network. Another topic concerns how training with specific stimuli aids in the establishment of a specific preference for those stimuli. That can be the focus of future investigations, however, we suggest that there should be an interplay of two related phenomena: The physical structure of certain neural circuits provides selective preference to the specified electric patterns, therefore various patterns of persistent electric stimuli can improve effectiveness to that stimuli. Furthermore, we agree with Nieus and colleagues' recent findings in hippocampal neural cultures [9] regarding state-dependent representation of stimulus-evoked activity, which was frequently indicated in our recordings and it could play an important role in seizure disorder management from a medical standpoint.

It was revealed that favored stimuli elicit gradually rising early and late responses, showing that diverse neural circuits involve gradually in information processing, on the one hand, and that early and late stages of sensory information processing may exist, on the other hand. Most research concentrate on short-term evoked responses, which reflect the features of fully established functional brain tissue. However, DCC symbolizes a developing neural circuitry at various phases, beginning with a colony of completely bare brain cells and progressing to a fully developed neural network. Certainly, the degree of activation of DCC's isolated neural networks differs significantly from that of *in vivo* neural tissue, as well as by some points for *in vitro* tissue culture, which is a major environmental determinant for development. Newly created neural connections of DCC obtain outside information from the electric stimuli delivered in our experimental settings that may be considered as a training for the existing synaptic connections. Usually, Increase of responses occurs repeatedly that could be associated to the restricted amount of the released neurotransmitter that need a time for rebuilding full synaptic capacity. On the other hand, it alludes to the gradual activation of the systems of information processing. The establishment of synapses is aided by training, which is a key aspect in the correct development of neural tissue. Simultaneously, it increases the probability of evoked responses in the

presence of favored stimuli, as demonstrated in our study.

Our experimental findings point to the importance of the later responses for the discrimination of stimuli as well that should be reflection of the prolonged neuroplasticity processes that could assist information coding especially in the developing neural circuits. Data show that generation of later responses also depend on the stimulus specify and are not present before they are applied. Literature findings are rare for those responses and the main accent fall on the evoked responses of short latency. However, several works indicate to the importance of delayed responses in the neural plasticity processes [10]. Instant evoked and delayed responses should reflect instant and delayed information processing, with the chance of quick responses rising after training sessions with preferred stimuli. It demonstrates the effect of synaptic plasticity for memory formation in response to favorable sensory input. At the same time, it emphasizes the progressive nature of information processing in order to memorize it.

5. Conclusions

1. The newly developed neural networks of DCC structure contain sufficient mechanisms for implementing sensory discrimination.
2. Sensory discrimination in DCC's neural circuits is a complex process with both immediate and delayed components that continues with training and produces favorable conditions for neuronal plasticity to memorize preferred stimuli and produce quick responses with increased probabilities.

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STUDY OF BLOOD FLOW IN MICROCIRCULATION VESSELS BY RESISTIVE ARTERIES FUNCTIONAL STATE INDEX

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Abstract

Resistive arteries in relation to blood flow have specific physiological significance. There are a lot of study of assessment of blood flow, but due attention is not paid to the function of resistive arteries as blood circulation regulators. Construction of a new method of resistive arteries will fill this gap. The article describes a new non-invasive method for study of blood flow in microcirculation vessels by resistive arteries functional state index, using indicates the resistance of resistive arteries. Resistance of resistive arteries is an easy-to-use diagnostic method for assessing circulatory problems. Our target group for check new method were young men. We made parallel study in this group, investigating erythrocyte aggregation and erythrocyte deformation index.

Keywords: rheology; microcirculation; resistive arteries

1. Introduction

The cardiovascular system consists of the heart and blood vessels - arteries, arterioles, capillaries, venules and veins, arterio-venous anastomoses. Its transport function lies in the fact that the heart ensures the movement of blood along a closed circuit of blood vessels. From the point of view of biomechanics, vessels are elastic tubes of various diameters. Distribution of total blood volume: 84% - in the systemic circulation, 9% - in the lesser circulation, 7% - in the heart [1].

In terms of elasticity, arteries are of the Elastic type. This is the aorta, the pulmonary artery; Muscular-elastic type these are sleepy, subclavian, vertebral arteria; muscle type - these are the arteries of the limbs, trunk, internal organs. Veins are of the Fibrous type. They are muscle less. Veins of the hard and soft

meninges (without valves); retina of the eye; bones, spleen, placenta. Veins are of the Muscular type: with muscle elements. These are the superior vena cava and its branches, veins of the face and neck; Veins are with an average development of muscle elements. These are the veins of the upper extremities. Veins are highly developed with strong muscle development. This is the inferior vena cava and its branches and veins of the lower extremities.

The structure of arteries and veins is as follows: intima is the inner shell, media is the middle, adventitia is the outer. All blood vessels are paneled from the inside with a layer of endothelium. All vessels have elastic, collagen and smooth muscle fibers. Their number in different vessels is different. They are not in true capillaries.

Depending on the function performed, the following groups of vessels are distinguished:

1. Amortizing vessels - aorta, pulmonary artery. The high content of elastic fibers in these vessels causes a shock-absorbing effect, which consists in smoothing out periodic systolic waves.

2. Resistive vessels - terminal arterioles (precapillaries) and, to a lesser extent, capillaries and venules. They have a small lumen and thick walls with developed smooth muscles, and offer the greatest resistance to blood flow.

3. Vessels-sphincters - terminal sections of precapillary arteriol. The number of functioning capillaries, that is, the area of the exchange surface, depends on the narrowing or expansion of the sphincters.

4. Exchange vessels - capillaries. The processes of diffusion and filtration take place in them. Capillaries are incapable of contractions, their diameter changes passively following pressure fluctuations in pre- and postcapillary resistive vessels and sphincter vessels.

5. Capacitive vessels are mainly veins. Due to their high elongation, veins are able to accommodate or eject large volumes of blood without significant changes in blood flow parameters, and therefore they play the role of a blood depot.

6. Bypass vessels - arterio-venous anastomoses. When these vessels are open, blood flow through the capillaries either decreases or stops completely [1,2,3].

We, as specialists in the study of hemodynamics and blood rheology, showed particular interest in the incomplete functional signs of resistive arteries being investigated. From the point of view of hemodynamics, blood circulation taps, which regulate the adequacy of blood circulation and ensure the required blood flow.

Hemodynamic bases. The flow of blood through the vessels. The driving force of blood flow is the pressure difference between different parts of the

vascular bed. Blood flows from a high-pressure area to a low-pressure area, from the high-pressure arterial section to the low-pressure venous section. This pressure gradient overcomes the hydrodynamic resistance due to internal friction between the liquid layers and between the liquid and the vessel walls, which depends on the size of the vessel and the viscosity of the blood.

The flow of blood through any part of the vascular system can be described by the formula for the volumetric blood flow velocity. Volumetric blood flow velocity is the volume of blood flowing through the cross-section of a vessel per unit time (ml/s). Volumetric blood flow velocity Q reflects the blood supply to a particular organ.

$Q = (P_2 - P_1)/R$, where Q is the volumetric blood flow velocity, $(P_2 - P_1)$ is the pressure difference at the ends of the vascular system, R is the hydrodynamic resistance.

The volumetric blood flow velocity can be calculated based on the linear blood flow velocity through the cross-section of the vessel and the area of this section:

$Q = V \times S$, where V is the linear velocity of blood flow through the cross-section of the vessel, S is the cross-sectional area of the vessel.

In accordance with the law of flow continuity, the volumetric blood flow velocity in a system of tubes of various diameters is constant regardless of the cross section of the tube. If a liquid flows through the tubes at a constant volumetric velocity, then the speed of movement of the liquid in each tube is inversely proportional to its cross-sectional area: $Q = V_1 \times S_1 = V_2 \times S_2$.

The viscosity of blood is a property of a liquid, due to which internal forces arise in it that affect its flow. If the flowing liquid comes into contact with a stationary surface (for example, when moving in a tube), then the layers of liquid move at different speeds. As a result, a shear stress arises between these layers: the faster layer tends to stretch in the longitudinal direction, while the slower one retards it. Blood viscosity is determined by blood cells and plasma proteins. Under physiological conditions, a laminar blood flow is observed in almost all parts of the circulatory system. The liquid moves as if in cylindrical layers, and all its particles move only parallel to the axis of the vessel. Separate layers of liquid move relative to each other, and the layer immediately adjacent to the wall of the vessel remains motionless, the second layer slides along this layer, the third layer over it, and so on. The result is a parabolic profile of the velocity distribution with a maximum in the center of the vessel. The smaller the diameter of the vessel, the closer the central layers of the liquid are to its stationary wall and the more they are inhibited as a result of viscous interaction with this wall. Due to the mean blood flow velocity is lower in small vessels. In large vessels, the central layers are

located farther from the walls, therefore, as they approach the longitudinal axis of the vessel, these layers slide relative to each other with increasing speed. As a result, the average blood flow velocity increases significantly [2]. Under certain conditions, the laminar flow turns into a turbulent one, which is characterized by the presence of vortices, in which fluid particles move not only parallel to the vessel axis, but also perpendicular to it. In turbulent flow, the volumetric blood flow velocity is proportional to the square root of the pressure gradient.

There are legalized principles of ultrasound examination. When studying them, the following are assessed: vessel permeability, vessel geometry, wall pulsations, vessel diameter; thickness, structure, uniformity of the wall; vessel lumen state.

Quantitative parameters are very important for clinical practice:

- peak systolic blood flow velocity (S);
- end diastolic blood flow velocity (D);
- time-averaged maximum blood flow velocity (TAMX);
- time-averaged mean blood flow velocity (Fmean, TAV);
- Peripheral resistance index, or resistivity index, or Pource-lot index (RI). $RI = S - D / S$;
- pulsation index, or index, or Gosling index (PI). $PI = S-D / Fmean$;
- spectral expansion index (SBI). $SBI = S - Fmean / S \times 100\%$;
- systolic-diastolic ratio (SD).

The spectrogram is characterized by many quantitative indicators, however, most researchers prefer the analysis of the Doppler spectrum based on not absolute, but relative indices [2].

Described by us above is the features of the study of hemodynamics in the arterial network. Features of hemodynamics in the veins are as follows.

Fluctuations in the velocity of blood flow in the great veins are associated with breathing and cardiac contractions. These fluctuations increase as you approach the right atrium. Fluctuations in pressure and volume in veins located near the heart (venous pulse) are recorded by non-invasive methods (using a pressure transducer) [1,4,5,6].

Compression of the vein lumen by the sensor leads to complete compression of the lumen. In the case of partial or complete thrombosis, the lumen of the vein is not completely compressed by the sensor or not compressed at all.

In the study of the venous system, in contrast to the arterial, fewer parameters are assessed.

In our early works, we paid special attention to the intima media layer for the evaluation of blood in general. All the methods described are especially

laborious, requiring special additional qualifications and experience from the meeting. For these methods, sophisticated equipment, specialized clinics and offices are required. The methods are financially expensive. But not only these questions prompted us to develop a particularly interesting method for evaluating blood circulation. This is a method for studying the functional state of resistive arteries.

In our early work, we paid particular attention to the intima media layer for blood flow assessment [7]. But this is a very painstaking process. At the moment, all methods are laborious, requiring special additional qualifications and experience from the doctor. These methods require sophisticated equipment, specialized clinics and offices. The methods are financially expensive. These and other questions prompted us to develop a new method for assessing blood circulation. This method is based on the study of the functional state of resistive arteries, determines the coefficient of microcirculation.

This article is methodological, overview and includes experimental data. The article presents a new method for studying the functional states of resistive arteries in order to diagnose somatic health in young men. The work was funded by the European University under a grant GR_EU001/ 08/2020.

2. Methods

The study included 53 healthy young people aged 22.4 ± 5.4 years. By means of special questionnaires, according to the analysis of the general blood picture (HumanCount, Germany), as well as by measuring the total arterial pressure ("Pulse" manometer, Russia), the condition of all volunteers was assessed, which corresponded to the definition of somatic health ("practically healthy"). The apparatus was used to study the functional state of resistive arteries at the site of pulsation using a standard test, measuring the coefficient of resistance of resistive arteries.

The coefficient of resistance of resistive arteries was denoted by the letter M, was calculated by the formula $M = (V_{pix}/V_{phon}) \times 100\%$, where V_{pix} is the volumetric blood flow velocity at the site of pulsation on the wrist after a standard ischemia with a duration of 1 min; V_{phon} is the rate of volumetric background blood flow at the

site of pulsation on the wrist without exposure. The coefficient of resistance of resistive arteries was measured as a percentage [7].

The measurement was based on a comparison of the blood flow velocity in postischemic (reactive) hyperemia resulting from a standard 60 cessation of local blood flow with the background blood flow at the site of pulsation at

the wrist. Standardized ischemia was induced by compression of the brachial artery, the blood flow curve was analyzed using a texture analysis apparatus (TAS-plus, Germany).

Following the Helsinki convention about scientific research, the participants were informed about the inclusion of the depersonalized method in the study, an informed consent was drawn up, which was signed by all volunteers included in the study addition to measuring the functional state of resistive arteries, we investigated the intravascular state of the blood, which forms the flow laminarity, or its turbulence [8]. Specifically, we measured the rate of erythrocyte aggregation [9], the rate of erythrocyte deformability in [10], plasma viscosity according to existing certified techniques [11].

3. Results and Discussion

When solving this problem, we studied a group of actually healthy young people. We examined for all members of the group the resistance of resistive arteries, the index of erythrocyte aggregation [EAI], the index of erythrocyte deformability [EDI], plasma viscosity. This comprehensive study enables us to study the vascular and extravascular factors that shape microcirculation and blood flow.

The statistically processed data showed that EAI, EDI and blood viscosity in the group of young people corresponded to the existing control (normative) values. See table 1.

Also, a homogeneous series of values of the functional value of resistive arteries was obtained, i.e. the resistance coefficient series did not have extrema and the scatter of values was minimal. This gave us the opportunity to conclude that the study of the functional state of the arteries is a diagnostic tool.

To check the validation of our new method, we examined patients with hemodynamic disorders with arterial obstruction syndrome: patients with stenosis (n=8) and patients with occlusion (n=9). All patients were examined for resistance of resistive arteries. 1. Syndrome in violation of arterial patency of varying degrees: patients with stenosis (n=5) and patients with occlusions (n=5); 2. Syndrom of arteriovenous shunting (n=6); 3. Syndrom of arterial vasodilation (n=5).

According to the literature, a decrease in the linear blood flow velocity can be recorded up to the deformation zone, and the peripheral resistance indices can be increased. In the deformation zone, there is an increase in the blood flow velocity, more often during bends, or multidirectional turbulent flow - in the case of loops. Behind the deformation zone, the blood flow velocity increases,

the peripheral resistance indices decrease. Since deformities develop for a long time, adequate collateral compensation develops.

It turned out that the resistance measured by our method turned out to be adequate, the one that was investigated by complex technological methods.

It occurs in the presence of arteriovenous fistulas, malformations. Changes in blood flow are noted in the arterial and venous bed. In the arteries proximal to the shunting site, an increase in the linear blood flow velocity, both systolic and diastolic, is recorded, the peripheral resistance indices are reduced. A turbulent flow is observed at the shunting site, its value depends on the shunt size, the diameter of the adducting and draining vessels. In the draining vein, the blood flow velocity is increased, often noted “arterialization” of venous blood flow, manifested by a “pulsating” Doppler curve. Having determined the resistance of resistive arteries in these patients with a new method, we obtained the same results.

This leads to a decrease in peripheral resistance indices and an increase in blood flow velocity in systole and diastole. It develops in systemic and local hypotension, hyper perfusion syndrome, “centralization” of blood circulation (shock and terminal states). In contrast to arteriovenous shunting syndrome, arterial vasodilation syndrome does not cause characteristic disorders of venous hemodynamics [1,2]. Research by our method showed similar results. Thus, within the framework of the grant, the results obtained can be interpreted as confirmation of a new diagnostic method with the aim of introducing and expanding this method into clinical medicine. Knowledge of the structure of the walls of blood vessels, their functions, the characteristics of hemodynamics in the arteries and veins is necessary for the successful prevention of hemodynamic disorders and proper treatment. Work in this direction is very timely, since the latest approaches in biomedicine include minimizing financial costs, patient safety and reducing the risk of errors on the part of the doctor. A new method for assessing the resistance of resistive arteries by examining the functional state of resistive arteries is safe, easy to implement and does not require large expenses against the background of high information content.

Table

Rheological properties in young men group. M - arithmetic mean of a row; m – arithmetic mean deviation from the mean of row. Row consists of 53 healthy young men

Parameters	M	m
EAI	23.5	0.2
EDI	2.0	0.02
Plasma viscosity	1.2	0.015

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POTENTIAL THERAPEUTIC VALUE OF PALOSURAN IN RENOVASCULAR HYPERTENSION AND ASSOCIATED CARDIO-VASCULAR AND RENAL COMPLICATIONS

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Abstract

Hypertension is the most common chronic disease in the world and produces substantial morbidity and mortality. Individuals with uncontrolled hypertension are at high risk of stroke, coronary artery disease leading to myocardial infarction, or acute renal failure. Nowadays, treatment of hypertension still remains a topical problem due to the side effects of existing antihypertensive drugs. In recent years, interest in the cyclic vasoactive neuropeptide urotensin-2 (U-II), which is characterized by strong

vasoconstrictor properties, has been increased. Increased secretion of U-II and excessive expression of UT-II receptors have been identified in several pathologies, including hypertension. Using U-II/UTR antagonists remain an attractive target in cardiovascular and renal system pathology. We were aimed to study effect of the UTR antagonist - Palosuran on blood pressure, cardiovascular system and renal tissue in rats with hypertension (2 kidneys+1 clip). Palosuran was administered intraperitoneally (10 mg/kg once daily, during 4 weeks). Blood pressure was measured non-invasively, using “tail cuff” method. Studies have shown that in hypertensive rats Palosuran reveals hypotensive effect, decreases workload on the myocardium and reduces risk of complications. Effect of treatment is better expressed at early stage of hypertension.

Keywords: Hypertension; Palosuran; cardio-vascular system; kidney

1. Introduction

Hypertension is the most common chronic disease in the world and produces substantial morbidity and mortality.

Individuals with uncontrolled hypertension are at high risk of stroke, coronary artery disease leading to myocardial infarction, or acute renal failure. Patients with hypertension and heart failure (HF) frequently have reduced kidney function. The links between the kidneys and cardiovascular system are being elucidated, with blood pressure (BP) being a key risk factor. In large HF registries, 20-68% of patients with hypertension and associated HF have moderate to severe kidney disease. The main goal of studying hypertension etio-pathogenesis in animal models is to foster the development of improved approaches to preventing and treating high blood pressure and its complications. Urotensin II (U-II) is a cyclic oligopeptide with vasoactive potential. It is currently one of the most potent vasoconstrictor known in mammals. The kidney is the major source of U-II in humans and animal species. The role of the U-II system in human physiology/pathophysiology is not yet fully understood. Increased plasma U-II concentrations have been associated with hypertensive disease, chronic heart failure and diabetes. Elevation in U-endogenous tone has also been recently demonstrated to contribute to the deterioration of renal function in rats [1].

Because of its potent vasoconstrictor effect, U-II attracted the interest of researchers in general hemodynamic. In fact, hemodynamic responses to U-II show regional heterogeneity in relation to its receptor localization, even in the differences of functional state of the endothelium.

U-II is a potent vasoconstrictor, but has some vasodilating properties in

specific vascular beds, notably in non diseased blood vessels via enhanced NO activity. The central action of U-II, in part mediated via the autonomic nervous system, leads to increased cardiac output and resultant higher BP. U-II is a constrictor of large resistive vessels. Conversely, it relaxes mesenteric vessels. U-II also plays a role in body fluid regulation, decreases glomerular filtration and increases renal sodium retention.

U-II action is brought about via activation of G-protein-coupled receptor 14 (GPR14). U-II increases inositol phosphate turnover and intracellular Ca^{++} . By activation of UTR, U-II might influence different pathways, depending on the cells and vascular compartment where the receptor is located.

UTR is expressed within the renal tubules, cardio vasculature (vascular smooth muscle, endothelium, myocardium etc.) and may, therefore, contribute to the physiological and pathophysiological regulation of cardiovascular homeostasis in humans. UTR are located peripherally on vascular smooth muscle and endothelial cells. Activation of UTR on vascular smooth muscle cells leads to contraction via RhoA/Rho-kinase activation (contractile responses) and activation of the endothelial UTR, leads to relaxation via NO formation (dilatory responses). In the kidney, UTR influences sodium and water homeostasis and glomerular filtration rate [2].

Studies have shown that U-II is upregulated in hypertension and UTR stimulation in the kidney, influences sodium and water homeostasis and glomerular filtration rate. U-II produces mesenteric vasodilation and portal hypertension in rats with secondary biliary cirrhosis [3]. Iontophoresis of U-II in healthy volunteers produces vasodilation (of the forearm), while in patients with heart failure or hypertension a constriction is observed.

Increased U-II expression in disease states has prompted the development of a number of UTR antagonists. There are preclinical and some clinical studies showing potential benefits of inhibiting U-II/UTR function in hypertension, heart failure, renal disease and diabetes that could be achieved using UTR antagonists.

One of the UTR antagonists - Palosuran (ACT-058362; 1-[2-(4-benzyl-4-hydroxy-piperidin-1-yl)-ethyl]-3-(2-methyl-quinolin-4-yl)-urea sulfate salt), in experimental studies revealed cardio-renal and metabolic protection in rat models of both ischemic and diabetic nephropathy [4]. Palosuran increased renal perfusion, glomerular filtration rate, renal sodium excretion, and improved renal function in cirrhotic rats supposedly due to direct effect of UTR blockade at the tubules and glomeruli. It lowered portal pressure via splanchnic vasoconstriction in these rats via activation of mesenteric vascular Rho-kinase and an inhibition of NO/cGMP-dependent PKG signaling.

Studies in other disease conditions are eagerly awaited. There are

epidemiologic data to support a relationship between U-II and human essential hypertension. In a study of 62 individuals with hypertension and 62 age-matched normotensive controls, plasma U-II levels were significantly higher in the hypertensive group and correlated positively with the systolic blood pressure. In addition, U-II excreted in urine was significantly higher in patients with essential hypertension than in normotensives and in patients with hypertensive renal disease compared to normotensive patients with renal disease [5]. In our preliminary studies conducted on rats with renovascular hypertension Palosuran revealed antihypertensive effect compared to control. Because the U-II/UTR is involved in cardiovascular system regulation UTR antagonism remains an attractive target in cardiovascular and renal system pathology and using U-II/UTR antagonists supposedly could have clinical potential and therapeutic benefit in patients with hypertensive disease and associated complications.

Coming from the aforesaid, we considered interesting to investigate effects of UTR antagonist - Palosuran on blood pressure, heart, kidney and mesenteric blood vessels in laboratory rats with renovascular hypertension.

2. Material and methods

The study was performed on 32 male Wistar rats weighing 200-250 g. after an adaptation period of at least 1 week. All rats were housed in the lab as a group of eight per cage in climate-controlled conditions with a 12-h light/dark cycle and free access to normal pelleted rat chow and drinking water.

The protocol used in this study for the use of rats as the animal model for research was overseen and approved by the Tbilisi State Medical University Animal Welfare and Use Ethics Committee (N39 - 17/08/2019).

For experimental modelling of hypertension, we used the reno-vascular (the two-kidney, one-clip - 2K1C) H. Goldblatt model. After separation of the renal artery from the vein and nerve the clip was placed on the left renal artery close to the aorta under general anaesthesia (Nembutal - 50 mg / kg).

The experimental animals were divided into 4 groups: Group I - healthy, intact rats; Group II - hypertensive rats; Group III - hypertensive rats, subjected to treatment with palosuran, started after 4 weeks of disease modelling;

Group IV - hypertensive rats, subjected to treatment with palosuran, started after 8 weeks of disease modelling.

Palosuran was injected intraperitoneally with the dose of 10 mg/kg, daily, during 4 weeks.

Blood pressure was measured non-invasively, using the systolic blood pressure measurement system (“tail cuff” method) once a week for 12 weeks.

Blood samples were obtained by jugular venous puncture after ketamine/xylazine anesthesia. Serum creatinine was measured using spectrophotometric method. The method explores the oxidation of p-methylamino phenol sulfate (Metol) in the presence of copper sulfate and creatinine which yields an intense violet colored species with maximum absorbance at 530 nm. Plasma renin concentration (PR) was measured using ELISA.

For evaluation of mesenteric arteries anaesthetized rats were placed on a heating plate at 37°C and a lateral laparotomy was performed. A short segment (2 cm) of the proximal part of the small intestine and mesentery was carefully pulled out. A segment of a branch of the mesenteric artery with the corresponding vein was placed into the reservoir filled with a physiological solution (PS). The other exteriorized tissue was kept moist using bandages soaked in PS. The arterial diameter was evaluated using microscopy.

Heart and kidney samples for morphological investigations were stained with hematoxylin-eosin dye. All statistical tests were conducted using IBM SPSS Statistics. Differences between control and treated animals were determined by using the Independent-Samples T test. The criterion for significance was set to $p < 0.05$.

3. Results

In experimental rats at different stages of the reno-vascular hypertension changes in mean arterial pressure (MAP) was detected compared to MAP of the group I animals (intact, healthy rats).

Results of experiment (Table 1) have shown that after 1 week of disease modelling, MAP was not increased significantly, after 2 weeks - MAP increased by 24% ($p < 0.05$), after 4 weeks, MAP increased by 42% ($p < 0.02$), after 8 weeks there was a significant increase in MAP by 44% ($p < 0.02$) and after 12 weeks of disease modelling, MAP was increased by 53% ($p < 0.001$) compared to MAP of the group I animals;

In healthy rats after administration of Palosuran MAP decreased by 33% ($p < 0.02$). In hypertensive rats on the 8th week of hypertension MAP was reduced by 32% ($p < 0.001$) compared to the control, untreated hypertensive rats and on the 12th week of hypertension, Palosuran revealed relatively less effect on MAP than at treatment started earlier. However, MAP was still reduced significantly by 23% ($p < 0.02$) compared to control group (untreated, hypertensive rats).

In hypertensive rats plasma renin (PR) concentration was increased progressively compared to the data of healthy rats. In palosuran-treated hypertensive rats PR was significantly lower than in untreated hypertensive

rats. After 1 week of disease modeling increase in PR by 4% was not statistically significant. After 2 weeks, PR was increased by 45% ($p<0,01$); After 3 weeks it was increased by 42% ($p<0,01$); After 4 weeks PR decreased and it was not statistically different compared to the norm, but after 8 weeks, PR was increased by 162% ($p<0,001$) and after 12 weeks, it was sharply increased by 234% compared to data of healthy rats.

Palosuran administration in healthy rats slightly decreased PR by 12% ($p>0,05$). After 8 weeks of disease modeling in hypertensive rats treatment with palosuran decreased PR by 33% ($p<0,01$) and after 12 weeks, PR was decreased by 24% ($p<0,01$) compared to data of untreated hypertensive rats. The serum creatinine level (SC) in rats after 4 weeks of disease modeling was not changed. SC on 8th week of hypertension was increased by 22,7% ($p<0,05$) and on 12th week of hypertension - by 45,4% ($p<0,01$).

In healthy rats after administration of Palosuran changes in SC were not statistically significant. In treated with Palosuran group animals after 8 weeks of disease modeling SC was decreased by 26% ($p<0,05$) and after 12 weeks of disease modeling, in palosuran-treated hypertensive rats, decrease in SC by 9,4% was not statistically significant (Table 1).

Table 1
Renin concentration and creatinine in healthy, hypertensive untreated and Palosuran-treated rats.

Rats	Without treatment		+ Palosuran	
	Renin (ng/ml)	Creatinine (mg/dL)	Renin (ng/ml)	Creatinine (mg/dL)
Intact, healthy rats	1,72±0,5	0,22±0.03	1,52±0,3	0,21±0.01
1st week of hypertension	1,79±0,3	-	-	-
2nd week of hypertension	2,49±0,4**	-	-	-
3rd week of hypertension	2,45±1,3**	-	-	-
4th week of hypertension	1,94±0,1	0,23±0.05	-	-
8th week of hypertension	4,5±1,4***	0,27±0.04*	3,02±0,9**	0,20±0.01*
12th week of hypertension	5,75±1,5***	0,32±0.03**	4,39±1,5**	0,29±0.02

* $p<0,05$, ** $p<0,01$, *** $p<0,001$

The diameter of mesenteric arteries (MA) in untreated hypertensive rats after 8 weeks of disease modeling were increased by 58% ($p < 0,001$) and by 25% ($p < 0,01$) on 12th week of hypertension compared to data of healthy rats.

The diameter of MA in Palosuran treated hypertensive rats after 8 weeks of disease modeling were decreased by 34,2% ($p < 0,001$) and by 23% ($p < 0,05$) on 12th week of hypertension compared to data of untreated hypertensive rats.

In Palosuran-treated hypertensive rats diameter of MA were not changed significantly compared to data of healthy rats. By the 8th week of disease modeling increase in MA by 4% and on 12th week of hypertension decrease by 5% was not significant.

Fig. 1 Diameter of mesenteric arteries in healthy, untreated and Palosuran-treated rats at different stages of reno-vascular hypertension.

According to the results of morphological investigations the healthy rats left ventricular size was 1,0mm, right - 0,2 mm; cardiomyocytes were within the norm (Fig. 1).

Fig. 2. Myocardial tissue of healthy rat. Staining H&E; x150. x250

After 8 weeks of disease modeling, in untreated hypertensive rats there was a slightly expressed left ventricular hypertrophy. Left ventricular size was 1,4mm, right - 0,21mm. Cardiomyocytes were within the norm. After 12 weeks of hypertension there was a well-expressed left ventricular hypertrophy. Left ventricular size was 2.0mm, right - 0,22mm.

In palosuran-treated rats by 8 weeks of hypertension myocardial hypertrophy was not detected. Left ventricular size was 1,07mm, right - 0,19mm. Slightly expressed hypertrophy was observed by 12th week of hypertension. Left ventricular size was 1,12mm and right - 0,21mm (Fig. 2).

Fig. 3. Myocardial tissue of healthy, untreated and Palosuran-treated rat at different stages of renovascular hypertension. H&E, x150.x250

A-Myocardial tissue of hypertensive rat (8th week);

B - Myocardial tissue of hypertensive rat (12thweek);

C - Myocardial tissue of Palosuran-treated hypertensive rat (8thweek);

D - Myocardial tissue of Palosuran-treated hypertensive rat (12thweek)

Morphological investigations of renal tissue in healthy rats have shown normal renal histoarchitecture with pronounced mild hyperemia. Glomerular and tubular apparatus was without pathology.

In hypertensive rats after 12 weeks of disease modeling there was intraglomerular hyperemia with RBC diapedesis, tubular dilatation and severe hyperemia.

In Palosuran-treated hypertensive rats 12 weeks after disease modeling tubular dilatation was detected without glomerular hyperemia and RBC diapedesis (Fig. 3).

Fig. 4. Renal tissue of healthy, untreated and Palosuran-treated rat at 12th week of renovascular hypertension.

A -Healthy rat (H&E, x250); B - Rat with renovascular hypertension (12th week. H&E, x250, x300); C - Palosuran-treated rat with renovascular hypertension (12th week. H&E, x250, x300)

4. Discussion

As the results of study have shown, statistically significant increase in blood pressure was created after 2 weeks of disease modeling. After 4 weeks, progressive increase in blood pressure was reliable and statistically significant. The increase in blood pressure at renovascular hypertension first of all develops due to the renal artery ischemia in the clipped kidney leading to ischemia, hypoxia, activation of the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system (RAAS), total peripheral vasoconstriction and water retention.

3 weeks after modelling of hypertension, reduction in MAP could be explained by the compensatory reaction of the second, intact kidney, decreasing rennin production and inhibiting RAAS system to restore homeostasis. However, on the 4 weeks of renovascular hypertension, compensatory reaction of the intact kidney fades away,

pressure regulatory system unable to maintain the blood pressure within the normal range and it increases significantly. At this stage of hypertension, increased blood pressure and MAP manifested in experimental animals supposedly is caused due to the complex action of RAAS and activated sympathetic nervous system. The latter, results in further increase in renin production and peripheral vasoconstriction.

Intraperitoneal treatment with Palosuran decreased antihypertensive effect of palosuran was demonstrated hypertension modeling) and at relatively late onset modeling).

blood pressure significantly in all study groups. The in both cases, at early treatment (started after 4 weeks of treatment (started after 8 weeks of hypertension).

Decreased MAP in all study groups of experimental animals could be explained by URT antagonistic effects of Palosuran [6]. However, it must be mentioned that at relatively late onset of treatment, the antihypertensive effect of Palosuran was lesser. According to the literature, U-II in a small doses induce the active production of NO (by activating NO-synthase) and consequently, the dilation of blood vessels as an endothelium-dependent vasodilator, but damaging effects of hypertension on blood vessels supposedly increases production of U-II and enhance the endothelium-independent vasoconstrictive effect of urotensin [27].

In hypertensive rats PR was increased progressively compared to the data of healthy rats. In palosuran-treated hypertensive rats PR was significantly lower than in untreated hypertensive rats.

In hypertensive rats by 2nd and 3rd weeks after disease modelling increase in PR 1.45- and 1.42-fold along with increased MAP develops due to renal ischemia. 4 weeks later, decrease in PR could be explained by a second, intact kidney-compensatory mechanism decreasing renin production.

High BP at the same period of hypertension in the presence of relatively low PR could be explained by increase in blood osmotic pressure, increase in circulating blood volume and increase in vascular basal tone due to hyperproduction of aldosterone, leading to the increased sodium reabsorption with further increase in blood osmolality and increased secretion of antidiuretic hormone, stimulating release of adrenocorticotrophic hormone and potentiating peripheral vasoconstriction [8].

The increase in basal tone supposedly is caused by an increase in the amount of Na⁺ in the blood vessel walls, leading to the water retention causing their swelling and thickening. In addition, Na⁺ increases sensitivity of α -adrenoceptors in blood vessel walls in response to catecholamine. Aldosterone also facilitates the release of norepinephrine from the sympathetic nerve endings and as a result, increases vascular neurogenic tone as well [9]. By the 8th week of disease modelling PR was increased 2,6-fold compared to the norm, and 3.34-fold by the 12th week of hypertension correlating with the data of systemic blood pressure and MAP.

Palosuran produced significant decrease in PR in all study group animals compared to control (especially in case of early onset of treatment), except in

healthy rats, where only a tendency of decrease in PR was observed. In healthy rats after administration of Palosuran arterial pressure and PR were not changed significantly that could be explained by the fact that urotensin production is relatively low in healthy rats, hence the effects of the palosuran is less respectively.

Increased SC in rats by 12th week of hypertension supposedly points on kidney malfunctioning. Although, Palosuran decreased SC in hypertensive rats at early onset of treatment the kidney spearing effect was not obvious at late stages of hypertension and late onset of treatment. Morphological investigations confirmed the renal and cardiac complications developed due to hypertension. Increased cardiac workload was reflected on myocardial hypertrophy and renal malfunctioning was manifested by intraglomerular hyperemia with RBC diapedesis, tubular dilatation and severe hyperemia. In Palosuran-treated rats due to normalization of renal hemocirculation, reduced MAP and decreased workload on heart muscle all investigated parameters were normalized, but only at the early stage of disease and early onset of treatment of hypertension.

Investigation of mesenteric arteries (MA) have shown that in hypertensive rats MA at early stage of disease was more dilated than later (by the 12th week of hypertension).

There is some evidence that U-II upregulates human and rat eNOS, which would suggest a hypothesis that U-II can cause arterial vasodilatation via NO, but causes vasoconstriction in diseased vessels without an intact endothelium. The activity of endothelial NO synthase (eNOS) has been shown to increase in hypertensive rats with elevated NO and cGMP production [10].

Nevertheless, reduced NO bioavailability has been established in hypertensive individuals, depending on the duration and severity of arterial hypertension. Indeed, in hypertensive rats, endothelium-derived constrictor factors (EDCFs) are produced, including angiotensin II, thromboxane A₂, and endothelin-1. The net result of EDCFs, reactive oxygen species (ROS) and NO production by endothelial cells in hypertensive rats is an impaired endothelial function and vasodilatation compared to normotensive rats.

Because at hypertension U-II concentration is increased we suppose that high concentration of U-II causes relaxation of mesenteric arteries through its endothelin-dependent vasodilatory properties and later, due to arterial damage eNOS upregulation vasodilatation via NO fades away and predominates endothelin-independent vasoconstriction. In mesenteric vessels, Palosuran supposedly upregulated expression of RhoA and Rho-kinase, increased Rho-kinase-activity, diminished nitric oxide (NO)/cyclic guanosine 3',5'-monophosphate (cGMP) signaling and produced vasoconstriction.

5. Conclusion

In summary, treatment with Palosuran, along with a decrease in blood pressure in rats, significantly reduces the workload on the myocardium and, therefore, reduces the risk of complications. Effect of treatment is better expressed at early stage of hypertension.

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The Scientific Study on Monitoring for the Scope Vocational Health Safety Systems, Salubrious and Beneficial Destitution Challenges According to the Covid Pandemic in Georgian Pharmaceutical Foundation Settings

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Abstract

Approaches to the activities of pharmaceutical institutions and the pharmaceutical business, in general, have always been a hot topic in Georgia. Therefore, the activities of pharmaceutical institutions require deeper study and supervision. Occupational safety and health in pharmaceutical enterprises is one of the components of labor rights and is a socio-economic law that includes a combination of labor rights and obligations, labor rights, a safe environment, regulation of compulsory working hours, fair working hours, fair or normal business hours. Equal treatment, non-discrimination, instrumental and other rights. Labor relations in different countries of the world are governed by various laws and regulations, international recommendations. The aim of the research was to study the monitoring for the scope vocational health safety systems, salubrious and beneficial destitution challenges according to the covid pandemic in Georgian pharmaceutical foundation settings. The purpose of the labor legislation in Georgia is to regulate the relationship between the employer and the employee through clearly defined legal regulation that excludes the exploitation of the employee and creates the possibility of work based on human dignity, freedom and self-development. Accordingly, the purpose of labor legislation is to regulate private legal relations at the normative level to the extent that it is necessary for the proper social protection of workers.

So equip the Labor Inspectorate with an unconditional and free access to the places of employment, which implies the authority of the mechanism, by its

own decision, to carry out inspections of the places of employment without the prior permission of the court.

Keywords: Monitoring; scope; occupational; safety; system; healthy; Covid-19; pharmaceutical foundation

1. Introduction

The performance of the assigned work is usually subject to organizational regulation and the daily and/or weekly hourly work schedule set by the employer. Under such organizational arrangements, it is important to classify time into work, break, and leisure time. Working time includes the time that an employee must use to fulfill a contractual obligation. Break time is the period of time between working hours, while break time is defined by labor law as leave periods and days off [1]. Depending on the specifics of the work, the Labor Code provides for additional leave for those working in heavy, harmful or hazardous work in the amount of 10 calendar days a year. The list of such works is approved by the order of the Minister for Internally Displaced Persons from the Occupied Territories of Georgia, Labor, Health and Social Protection [2,3].

The employer is obliged to provide the employee with the safest working environment for health. The need for individual measures to protect and maintain the health of employees is particularly high in some areas of employment. Periodic and regular medical examinations are required depending on the content of the activity. With the exception of cases provided for by a regulatory enactment, the employer has the right to determine additional conditions for a medical examination [4]. Working conditions. An important prerequisite for the rational use of employees' working time and, in general, for increasing the efficiency of their work are normal working conditions and the establishment of rational internal rules for work and rest at the enterprise. Work should be carried out in normal, favorable conditions, and when planning a workplace and its technological equipment, it is necessary to take into account the latest advances in technology and technology. This significantly helps to reduce staff fatigue, save time, improve staff efficiency and ultimately improve work efficiency and success [5,6].

Safety and social resilience include: protecting employees' rights and safe working conditions, preventing human trafficking and eliminating child labor. In pharmaceutical institutions, hygiene standards are required and adhered to. Pharmacy institutions are all institutions in which pharmaceutical activities are carried out. When carrying out pharmaceutical activities under the influence of high-risk factors, possible cases of occupational diseases

of an employee may develop [7,8]. An occupational disease (acute or chronic) develops under the influence of factors that threaten the working environment and the production process, causes a deterioration in his health and/or restriction of his professional ability to work in the short or long term, and is determined by the legislation of Georgia [9,10].

Therefore, the specifics of pharmaceutical activities should be taken into account, in particular: the development of a new pharmaceutical product (molecule), the use of various chemicals and technologies, which, in turn, require special precautions. Also, one cannot ignore the necessary characteristics during storage, transportation, delivery, consumption of finished products, and, as a result, the need to comply with sanitary and hygienic working conditions [11].

Related to the pharmaceutical industry: measures related to waste collection, processing, waste disposal, pollution control and other waste management processes. Therefore it is necessary to consider:

1. Sanitary-hygienic characterization of working conditions - physical, chemical, biological factors of the production and/or working environment and the labor process;

2. The permissible norms of chemical substances in the air of the working zone of the pharmaceutical institution shall be used for the hygienic assessment of the working conditions for the following purpose:

- A) To determine the conformity with the hygienic norms to check the working conditions of the employees and to make a hygienic conclusion;

- B) To determine the priority direction during the implementation of remedial measures and to determine its effectiveness;

- C) To create a database at the level of enterprise, field, region, republic;

- D) To determine the level of occupational risk, to take preventive measures and to justify social protection measures;

- E) To investigate cases of occupational diseases and poisoning.

These rules set out the organizational and technical measures, as well as the requirements for the prevention (or reduction of the degree of impact) and safety of impact and hazardous impact factors. Occupational safety issues in the workplace, existing and expected threats, accident and occupational disease prevention, staff training, information, counseling and their equal involvement in occupational safety and health issues.

The norms of high hierarchy to be used for labor protection purposes are the Constitution of Georgia; Conventions of international organizations related to labor safety, remuneration, product certification and similar issues, relevant laws, and by-laws.

Labor protection in modern conditions is practically the same component of

management, such as optimization of management by raising the qualification of staff; Expansion of the key market (by improving the quality of services and products provided); Perfection of technology and production infrastructure. The sanitation of the institution serves to eliminate the harmful conditions for people in the workplace and to improve the production factors by using sanitary-technical means [12,13]. Harmful conditions are considered to be factors that affect people causing their illness or reduced ability to work. Naturally, this needs to be addressed through proper organizational issues. Safety equipment is organizational, technical measures, technical means, proper staff habits that reduce the impact of dangerous factors on human life and health. Dangerous are factors that in the shortest amount of time lead to trauma or a sharp deterioration in health [14,15].

Harmful conditions, in some cases, may be conducive to the appearance of hazardous factors at work and increase the likelihood of receiving an industrial injury. For example, dim lighting, high noise levels, etc. It distracts a person and increases the likelihood of receiving an industrial injury. In addition, adverse conditions are sometimes directly attributable to industrial trauma — acute illness as a result of exposure to one shift or less. For example, poisoning with nitrogen, carbon monoxide (oxides) or other toxic impurities, etc. Fire safety means the creation of a system of passive and active organizational-technical measures to prevent its occurrence, which, if necessary, involves evacuation. The system is passive if hard-to-reach materials and equipment are used, making fires less likely to occur under proper conditions [16,17].

We must remember that most of the expected danger in this or that process was revealed after it happened to a person. In view of the above, strict adherence to safety rules is a matter of public need and it is not just a personal matter (of the employer or the employee). Consequently, when concluding a contract, the parties must not only agree on the level of security, but also the level of security provided in each case must be in accordance with the law [18, 19]. Accordingly, safety rules can be formulated on sectoral, technological and other principles. Safety is such an important value that all its interpretations are acceptable given the task of fully mastering and understanding the material [20]. Particular attention in the found literature is paid not only to the protection of safe conditions for the employee, but also plays an important role in the means of avoiding safety by the employee himself. This requires the creation of a self-safe environment, which, first of all, provides for the necessary compliance of sanitary and hygienic norms by the employee, in particular, it is important to process hands in specially designated places, hand washing in the dishwasher is prohibited [21,22].

For hand disinfection use 70% ethyl alcohol and any alcohol preparation

(octoriderm, octonecept), 0.5% chlorhexidine bigluconate (70% ethyl alcohol), iodopyrone solution and others, 1% iodide iodine, 0.5% B chloramine solution (if no other drugs) and other remedies authorized by the Ministry of Refugees, Labor, Health and Social Affairs from the Occupied Territories. If the activity is related to research work, in this case an additional condition is to wash your hands with warm water and treat them with emollients such as a mixture of glycerin, alcohol, 10% ammonia and an equal amount of water, which is thoroughly shaken before use. Other emollients, ready-made creams that provide elasticity and durability to the skin of the hand can be used [23,24].

In pharmaceutical establishments special attention should be paid to the lighting factor. Because it is possible that failure to take precautionary measures will harm not only the employee but also the quality of the pharmaceutical product. It is necessary to protect the bactericidal emitters, which are low pressure air discharge lamps, 254 nm. With wavelengths of ultraviolet radiation corresponding to the area of greatest bactericidal action of the radiant energy [25,26].

Two types of emitters are known. Non-screen lamps - for rapid disinfection of the surface and air (in the absence of people). The set power of non-screen lamps should not exceed 2-2.5 watts of power consumed from the mains per 1 m³ of storage space. With screen lamps - for irradiation of the upper layers of air (in the presence of humans), at this time the lower layers are neutralized by convection. The set capacity of the screen

lamps shall not exceed 1 watt of the power consumed from the mains per 1 m³ of storage space. Screen bactericidal lamps can work up to 8 hours a day. If there is not enough ventilation, after 1.5-2 hours of continuous operation of the lamps, a characteristic odor of ozone will be felt in the air, it is recommended to turn off the lamps after 30-60 minutes [32]. The pharmaceutical facility is subject to constant cleaning. In this case it is necessary to take into account - the safety of personnel engaged in the use of disinfectant and disinfectant solutions. Clothing should consist of a robe, a hat and rubber gloves. At the time of dosing the drug it is necessary to use protective goggles and a respirator (or a four-layer Dolbandi bandage). When perhydrol gets on the skin it should be rinsed off immediately with water. When chlorine powder gets on the skin, this part of the skin should be washed with soap and water and treated with a 2% solution of sodium hyposulfite or sodium bicarbonate [27,28].

Pharmaceutical establishments are obliged to have fire-fighting and safe activities, in accordance with the Law of Georgia on Civil Safety, and other normative acts in the field of fire safety, to have: Pursuant to paragraph 2 of Article 21 and paragraph 1 of Article 24 of the Law of Georgia on Civil Safety,

the powers of the executive bodies of Georgia in the field of fire safety and the powers delegated to the municipalities are defined. Municipalities shall exercise the powers defined by this Technical Regulation only in accordance with the delegation of powers in accordance with Article 24, Paragraph 2 of the Law of Georgia on Civil Security.

Prior to the commencement of the research in the scientific laboratories, the supervisor is obliged to instruct the personnel on the fire safety measures:

1. The head of the experiment is responsible for observing the fire safety requirements during the experiments;
2. Stocks of flammable and combustible liquids and combustible substances should be stored in specially arranged compartments (cells);
3. Chemical reagents that may interact with each other, water and air may cause fire or explosion, should be stored separately, in appropriate packaging, in dry closets. Jars, bottles and other packaging where chemical reagents and substances are stored must be labeled with the characteristic hazards: “fire hazardous”, “explosive”, “poisonous”, “chemically active”. Flammable and combustible liquids and gases in laboratory warehouses must be supplied to the workplace in packed and container-safe containers;
4. All work in laboratory warehouses, accompanied by the release of explosive fire vapor and gas, should be carried out in the exhaust cabinets. It is forbidden to carry out works in exhaust cabinets that have faulty ventilation;
5. Upper and lower air intake should be provided in the exhaust cabinets, if the work carried out is accompanied by the release of flammable vapors and gases;
6. Laboratory tables and exhaust cabinets designed to work with flammable liquids and combustible gases, as well as with flammable substances, shall be made of non-combustible materials;
7. Do not spill flammable and combustible liquids into the sewer;
8. Fire safety signs prohibiting the use of open fire shall be posted on fire hazardous premises and fire-hazardous equipment;
9. Chemicals and materials should be stored in separate storage units in groups according to uniformity of physical, chemical and fire hazardous properties;
10. During the storage of nitrogen and sulfuric acid, measures should be taken to exclude their contact with wood materials and other substances of organic origin;
11. Storages where chemicals capable of thawing during a fire should be stored should be provided with means to limit the free flow of thaw (chemicals, thresholds).

Each facility / enterprise must keep information on the hazard indicators

of the substances and materials (including by-products, waste) used in technological processes. It is not allowed to use substances and materials in the technological processes of enterprises, the explosion hazard indicators of which have not been studied. When storing and transporting substances and materials, their aggregate condition, the possibility of joint storage, as well as the uniformity of their extinguishing means, the rule of Annex 8 - storage of substances and materials - should be taken into account, taking into account the requirements [29-31].

Repair work on industrial premises, technological apparatus and equipment, as well as on premises where technological processes related to the release of hazardous dust, steam and gases are underway. Repair and re-equipment of ventilation units is allowed only if Meanings. During the works, the repair apparatus (unit) or the ventilation system area should be disconnected from other areas. In a pharmaceutical institution (pharmacies, training and scientific research laboratories) the responsibility for compliance with fire safety requirements rests with the head of the institution and / or the person designated by the order. There should be an evacuation place for employees on the territory of the institution with the inscription "evacuation place" [18,19,25].

After a long break (more than 1 hour), disconnect electrical appliances (except computers, refrigerators and fax machines) from the electrical outlet; Disconnect the electrical appliances and equipment in the storeroom from the power source. After finishing work, inspect the pharmacy, enterprise, training and scientific research laboratory, room, storeroom, before closing, close all windows, turn off all electrical appliances and lighting.

Stocks of flammable and flammable liquids and volatile / flammable substances should be stored in specially designed containers (limit amount) [14,15,24].

Chemical reagents that may interact with each other, water and air may cause fire or explosion, should be stored separately, in appropriate packaging, in fireproof cabinets. All work in the storerooms, accompanied by the release of poisonous, explosive and flammable vapors and gases, should be carried out in the exhaust cabinets. It is forbidden to carry out works in exhaust cabinets that have faulty ventilation. Tables and hoods designed to work easily and with flammable liquids and combustible gases, as well as with flammable substances, must be made of non-combustible materials. Do not allow flammable and volatile liquids to enter the sewer. There should be a place in the facility with appropriate special utensils for placing liquid and solid waste (separately), which is removed from the facility by a special service. Fire safety signs and fire-hazardous equipment must be affixed with fire safety signs prohibiting the use of open fire.

Chemicals and materials should be stored in separate storage units in groups according to their uniformity of physical, chemical and toxic, fire-hazardous properties. Do not allow nitrogen and sulfuric acid to come into contact with wood materials and other substances of organic origin during storage. Storage where flammable chemicals are stored should be subject to a free-flow limit [9,16]. Hygienic norms in Georgia are compiled on the basis of recognized international standards, on the principle of specificity of regulation (allergen, carcinogen, irritant, etc.). Hygienic norms provide information on chemicals are presented in the form of summary tables in the appendices, where the following data on each substance are given: chemical name (in alphabetical order), ZDC values (mg/m³), aggregate condition, hazard classes, case of biological impact, number Notes with reference to standard safety phrases [6,9,16,19].

Requirements for the marking and labeling of hazardous chemicals should be taken into account in the state standards and normative-technical documents regulating the field of chemicals management.

From a safety point of view, special importance is attached to the transportation of a pharmaceutical product, which is set out in the same Act as follows:

1. In case of transportation of a chemical substance, the label of the transport container shall include additional information on the number of packed container places placed in the transport container, the net and gross mass of each place, an indication on the normative-technical documentation;

2. If it is practically impossible to label and mark the container of a hazardous chemical due to the size of the container or the nature of the packaging, the relevant information must be reflected in the attached documentation;

3. Requirements for marks include:

A) The markings on the label must reflect accurate information about the hazardous chemical;

B) The label must be firmly attached to the container. Its size must comply with the requirements set by the norms. The inscription should be clear and easy to understand;

(C) Labels with signs and symbols depicted on them must be uniform, including the R-phrases of risk and the S-phrases of safety used in the colors used [27,28,30].

This document addresses the safety issues of the pharmaceutical product in pharmaceutical establishments, as well as the cases when the patient uses the pharmaceutical product.

The Ministry of Labor, Social Affairs, and the Ministry of Internally Displaced Persons from the Occupied Territories of Georgia (hereinafter referred to as the Ministry) is the Labor Safety Supervision Authority in Georgia. Protecting the health of the employed population, preventing occupational

and occupational diseases, promoting a safe environment in the workplace. The beneficiaries of the program are citizens of Georgia. The program provides state-sponsored occupational health research for various services, including state-owned enterprises [26,27,28].

By the decree of the Government of Georgia, the state program for monitoring the working conditions was approved, the implementation of which was entrusted to the central office of the Ministry. The target group of the program includes employers who give their prior consent to the monitoring. In addition, under this program, employers receive a notification about the inspection 5 working days before the monitoring procedure. Within the program, the target group is selected and the monitoring sequence is determined. The program does not establish the rules for conducting monitoring and its regulation is linked to the issuance of an individual act of the Minister. Violation of labor safety norms is controlled by a labor safety specialist - a person with appropriate qualifications appointed/ invited by the employer, who ensures the introduction and management of labor safety measures to prevent violations of labor safety norms [11,12,15].

Occupational safety is a broad commandment and encompasses in itself a safe environment saturated with sanitary norms, primarily the safe use of medicines, subject to all conditions. This determines not only their quality, but also the prevention of a dangerous environment for the population and employees. It should be noted that all the requirements necessary for contact with a product saturated with chemical properties, as well as the extent to which working conditions are observed, including normalized working hours, temperature regime, degree of pollution, fire condition, as well as other unforeseen cases, must be lawfully observed [29,31].

Therefore, the study and evaluation of the legal-normative basis of labor safety, equipment and sanitary-hygienic requirements of the activities of Georgian pharmaceutical companies is quite relevant. The study is multifaceted in its problems, so it is discussed from different angles, including in the context of the security situation in the country. Accordingly, the paper covers, as far as possible, problems related to the fulfillment of labor safety, equipment and sanitary-hygienic requirements, as well as ways to eliminate and solve them.

Aim and Objectives of the Research

The aim of the research was to study the monitoring for the scope vocational health safety systems, salubrious and beneficial destitution challenges according to the covid pandemic in Georgian pharmaceutical foundation settings.

The legal-normative basis of labor safety, equipment and sanitary-hygienic requirements of activities in pharmaceutical institutions, to identify their strengths and weaknesses, pros and cons, to reflect a specific problem and to find ways to solve, eliminate and resolve it. In order to achieve the above-mentioned goal, we considered it necessary to determine the quality and compliance of the work space safety of the research facilities with the Organic Law of Georgia on Labor Safety. Assessing the risk of harm to personnel and consumers was considered an existing epidemic. Regarding safety - according to the data of the study period.

2. Materials and Methods

The information source of the paper is the materials of the survey of pharmacists, international economic journals, reports of the Ministry of Internally Displaced Persons from the Occupied Territories, Labor, Health and Social Affairs, statistical collections of the State Department of Statistics, Georgian laws, bylaws and other legal acts.

In general, the subject of research was the Georgian pharmaceutical market, which creates a danger not only for consumers but also for employees. The objects of research are pharmacies operating in the market, pharmaceutical companies, pharmaceutical companies, regulatory bodies and employees working there. Based on the existing theoretical foundations of occupational safety, we considered it necessary to identify the methodological and practical issues, the set of materials from which we selected the objects of research. The 2 types of questionnaires for pharmacists were selected. The questionnaire, on the one hand, considers whether there is a regulatory legal framework on labor safety in Georgia and, on the other hand, whether all the requirements provided by the legal framework are met, to what extent they comply with the requirements and standards.

Through this questionnaire, we focused on the following key issues:

- What information do pharmacists have about occupational safety, including sanitation;
- Is labor safety in pharmaceutical institutions regulated in Georgia;
- Is there a legal normative basis for sanitary requirements;
- If regulated, then how much is actually done in pharmaceutical establishments;
- Whether employees are provided with information on safety rules when hired and whether there is an appropriate entry in the employment contract.

3. Research Results and Discussion

The target segment of the research was 5 objects: 2 of them were pharmaceutical factories: GMP Ltd; Neopharm Ltd. Two Drugstores” Pharmacy PSP Ltd; Aversi-Pharma Ltd; And the regulatory body. Ministry of Internally Displaced Persons from the Occupied Territories, Labor, Health and Social Affairs of Georgia, LEPL Agency for Regulation of Medical and Pharmaceutical Activities. The answers to each question from each of the five objects are presented in summary form (we did not consider it necessary to present the results separately at this stage). With this we tried to present an overall picture of the data actually available. The survey was conducted with a pre-compiled questionnaire, the anonymity of the respondents was protected. The start date of the study was October 2019, which lasted until May 2020. Thus, the data were collected, which we conditionally divided before the COVID-19-related contraction (February) and during the COVID-19 activation period. In both cases, due to the current situation, we used the same topical questions. Accordingly, an average of 142 respondents (from all five facilities) were interviewed. The answers are presented with two data. All the first diagrams presented are data up to COVID-19. Second, even the data obtained during COVID-19.

The data show that 30.3% of the respondents did not know about the regulation of occupational safety in a pharmaceutical facility before the pandemic. In the conditions of the pandemic, the interest in this direction increased by 40.0% and also the number of respondents who were unaware decreased from 36% to 28.1% from 8.5%, which somehow indicates a necessary tendency for self-development. See Table 1.

Table 1
Q 1. Is labor safety regulated in pharmaceutical institutions?

Before Covid-19 (%)		Differences (%)	During Covid-19 (%)	
Yes	30.3	40.0	Yes	70.3
No	33.1	11.9	No	21.2
I do not know	36.6	28.1	I do not know	8.5

The answers to the question about the degree of informativeness about the sanitary requirements of the legal normative base in pharmaceutical institutions do not look very good. The data show that it seems that all respondents are

familiar with this issue, but it seems that the current situation also played a role here and the degree of improvement of knowledge amounted to - 31.9%. See Table 2.

Table 2
Q 2. Do you know the legal normative based on sanitary requirements?

Before Covid-19 (%)		Differences (%)	During Covid-19 (%)	
Yes	41.8	319	Yes	73.7
No	58.2	31.9	No	26.3
I do not know	-	-	I do not know	-

Unfortunately, 31.1% of respondents did not have information about the regulation of sanitary requirements. In this regard and 34.5% believed that it was not regulated. But in a re-survey, informatics increased by 45.6%, with 78% believing it to be regulated. The number of those who did not know decreased by 28% to 5.1%. See Table 3.

On this question, we think that the level of informatics is low and it should also be noted that before the pandemic and during the pandemic, interest in this area changed by only 9.0%. There are small gaps between the responses of respondents who do not know whether accounting is taking place. See Table 4. Interest in hiring employers to learn about occupational safety rules increased from 49.3% to 72% to 22.7%. Respondents who did not know and were not informed when hiring accounted for 50.0% which decreased by 22.7% and amounted to 28%. It should be noted that a high rate would be high on all of the above questions to maintain a high degree of information on all occupational safety regulations when hiring. We think that this information is important and should be taken into account. See Table 5.

It is noteworthy that 48.9% of respondents in the workplace believe that occupational safety is protected and 51% state that it is not protected, which changed significantly during the pandemic and increased by 30%. We think more attention is needed in this direction. See Table 6.

It is unfortunate that 50% were unaware of the existence of health hazards in the workplace and the degree of interest in information during the pandemic changed by 37.6% to 87.2%. It should definitely be noted that pharmaceutical activity is associated with life-threatening substances. And especially if the touch is long. See Table 7.

Before the pandemic, 62.1% said that during the pandemic - 94.9%, according

to the survey results, during the pandemic, the number of medical institutions where the evacuation board was posted increased by 32.5%. It is known that the evacuation board is a plan of the floors of a building (pharmacy), which shows the evacuation exits, rescue facilities and their locations, etc. The spread of the evacuation board in the pharmacy was due to the sharply increased number of patients in pandemic conditions and the stressful environment created by the situation caused the pharmacists to lose attention, thus increasing the risk of harmful events (flammable substance ignition, fire hazard, etc.). See Table 8.

Table 3

Q 3. Are sanitary requirements regulated in pharmaceutical facilities?

Before Covid-19 (%)		Differences (%)	During Covid-19 (%)	
Yes	32.4	45.6	Yes	78
No	34.5	17.6%	No	16.9
I do not know	33.1	28	I do not know	5.1

Table 4

Q 4. On the territory of Georgia, is there any registration of occupational disease at work with the existing high-risk, severe, harmful hazardous conditions?

Before Covid-19 (%)		Differences (%)	During Covid-19 (%)	
Yes	41.8	9.0	Yes	50.8
No	25.5	0.8	No	26.3
I do not know	32.6	9.7	I do not know	22.9

Table 5

Q 5. Did the employer introduce you to the rules of labor safety when hiring you?

Before Covid-19 (%)		Differences (%)	During Covid-19 (%)	
Yes	49.3	22.7%	Yes	72
No	50.7	22.7	No	28
I do not know	-	-	I do not know	-

Table 6

Q 6. Is there occupational safety at your workplace?

Before Covid-19 (%)		Differences (%)	During Covid-19 (%)	
Yes	48.9	30.8	Yes	79.7
No	51.1	30.8	No	20.3
I do not know	-	-	I do not know	-

Table 7

Q 7. Are you aware of the health risk factors in your workspace?

Before Covid-19 (%)		Differences (%)	During Covid-19 (%)	
Yes	49.6	37.6	Yes	87.2
No	50.4	37.6	No	12.8
I do not know	-	-	I do not know	-

Table 8

Q 8. Is there an evacuation board/drawing in your workspace?

Before Covid-19 (%)		Differences (%)	During Covid-19 (%)	
Yes	62.4	32.5	Yes	94.9
No	37.6	32.5	No	5.1
I do not know	-	-	I do not know	-

Almost all respondents to this question state that psycho-social factors should be taken into account in the institution. And positive responses, i.e. necessity before pandemic and pandemic time difference was 16%. Difference (66.2% before pandemic and 82.2% during pandemic). But it should also be noted that 33.8 (19 + 14.8) does not know the psycho-social factors should be taken into account in the institution. See Table 9.

Table 9

Q 9. Do you think the institution should take into account psycho-social factors (stress, communication, post-traumatic stress)?

Before Covid-19 (%)		Differences (%)	During Covid-19 (%)	
Yes	66.2	16	Yes	82.2
No	19	2.1	No	16.9
I do not know	14.8	13.9	I do not know	0.9

Quite interesting answers to the question of whether safety rules need to be learned. In both cases, the difference between the responses of the respondents is small and 13%. Nearly 90% believe that occupational safety needs to be taught. And as far as I know to date this issue is included in the Pharm Case and Organization and Economics curriculum. See Table 10.

Table 10

Q 10. Do you think if it is necessary to teach labor safety rules as a discipline?

Before Covid-19 (%)		Differences (%)	During Covid-19 (%)	
Yes	84.5	13	Yes	97.5
No	15.5	13	No	2.5
I do not know	-	-	I do not know	-

It is noteworthy that before the pandemic, 36.6% of respondents reported that there were no dezo-barriers in pharmacies. The results of the survey differ significantly from the data obtained during COVID-19 infection. 99.9% of respondents confirm that there are dezo barriers in pharmacies. See Table 11.

Table 11

Q 11. Is there a dezo-barrier in the pharmaceutical facility / pharmacy?

Before Covid-19 (%)		Differences (%)	During Covid-19 (%)	
Yes	63.4	36.5	Yes	99.9
No	36.6	36.5	No	0.1
I do not know	-	-	I do not know	-

4. Conclusions

Based on the study of the problems of this issue and the results of the research, we can draw the following conclusions:

- We believe that the right, legal approach, strict control and state policy in the field of drug trafficking are a prerequisite for creating a safe environment. Most importantly, despite the interests of the owners of the Georgian pharmaceutical industry and modern marketing approaches, the safety of the population and employees remains a priority;
- 44.3% of respondents are not informed about labor safety regulations in Georgia;
- Low legal-normative base and level of awareness on sanitary requirements in pharmaceutical institutions;
- Expand the scope of the draft law on labor safety and extend it to all places of employment, without exception;
- Equip the Labor Inspectorate with an unconditional and free access to the places of employment, which implies the authority of the mechanism, by its own decision, to carry out inspections of the places of employment without the prior permission of the court.

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